

Mualij

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Mualij

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Declaration

I declare that the work contained in this thesis is my own, except where explicitly stated otherwise. In addition this work has not been submitted to obtain another degree or professional qualification.

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Dedicated to our immediate Families and Friends

Contents

Acknowledgments	iii
List of Figures	vii
List of Tables	viii
Abbreviations	xii
Abstract	xiii
1 Introduction	1
1.1 Introduction	1
1.2 Objectives	2
1.3 Project Statement	2
1.4 Project Scope	2
2 Requirement Analysis	4
2.1 Literature Review	4
2.1.1 Heart Disease Prediction	4
2.1.2 Pneumonia Detection	7
2.2 Requirement Elicitation	9
2.2.1 Functional Requirements	9
2.2.2 Non-Functional Requirements	10
2.3 Use Case Diagram	11
2.4 Use Cases	12
3 System Design Analysis	19
3.1 Activity Diagrams	19
3.2 Class Diagrams	33
3.3 Sequence Diagrams	34
4 System Implementation	46
4.1 Proposed Methodology	46
4.1.1 Heart Disease Prediction	46
4.1.2 Pneumonia Detection	49
4.2 Tools and Technologies	52

List of Figures

2.1	Use Case Diagram	11
3.1	Login Activity Diagram	19
3.2	Account Registration Activity Diagram	20
3.3	Create Post Activity Diagram	21
3.4	Delete Post Activity Diagram	22
3.5	Interact with Post Activity Diagram	23
3.6	AI Model Prediction Activity Diagram	24
3.7	Profile Management Activity Diagram	25
3.8	Search Post Activity Diagram	26
3.9	Create Community Activity Diagram	27
3.10	Edit Community Activity Diagram	28
3.11	Add Moderators Activity Diagram	29
3.12	Join Community Activity Diagram	30
3.13	Award Post Activity Diagram	31
3.14	Remove Post Activity Diagram	31
3.15	Get Verified as Doctor Activity Diagram	32
3.16	Class Diagram	33
3.17	Login with Google Sequence Diagram	34
3.18	Login with email Sequence Diagram	34
3.19	Account Registration with Google Sequence Diagram	35
3.20	Account Registration with Email Sequence Diagram	35
3.21	Create Post Sequence Diagram	36
3.22	Delete Post Sequence Diagram	37
3.23	Interact with Post Sequence Diagram	38
3.24	AI Model Prediction Sequence Diagram	38
3.25	Profile Management Sequence Diagram	39
3.26	Search Post Sequence Diagram	39
3.27	Create Community Sequence Diagram	40
3.28	Edit Community Sequence Diagram	40
3.29	Add Moderators Sequence Diagram	41
3.30	Join Community Sequence Diagram	42
3.31	Award Post Sequence Diagram	43
3.32	Remove Post Sequence Diagram	44
3.33	Get Verified as Doctor Sequence Diagram	45

List of Tables

2.1	Use Case: Sign In	12
2.2	Use Case: Account Registration	12
2.3	Use Case: Create Post	13
2.4	Use Case: Delete Post	13
2.5	Use Case: Interact with Post	14
2.6	Use Case: AI Model Prediction	14
2.7	Use Case: Profile Management	15
2.8	Use Case: Search Post	15
2.9	Use Case: Create Community	16
2.10	Use Case: Edit Community	16
2.11	Use Case: Add Moderators	17
2.12	Use Case: Join Community	17
2.13	Use Case: Remove Post	18
2.14	Use Case: Remove Community	18
5.1	Unit Test TC-01A – Signup Using Continue with Google (Empty Fields)	54
5.2	Unit Test TC-01B – Signup Using Continue with Google (Incorrect Google Account)	55
5.3	Unit Test TC-01C – Signup Using Continue with Google (Successful Signup)	56
5.4	Unit Test TC-02A – Signup Using Email (Empty Fields)	57
5.5	Unit Test TC-02B – Signup Using Email (Invalid Email Format)	58
5.6	Unit Test TC-02C – Signup Using Email (Weak Password)	59
5.7	Unit Test TC-02D – Signup Using Email (Email Already Exists)	60
5.8	Unit Test TC-02E – Signup Using Email (Successful Signup)	61
5.9	Unit Test TC-03A – Login Using Email and Password (Empty Fields)	62
5.10	Unit Test TC-03B – Login Using Email and Password (Incorrect Credentials)	63
5.11	Unit Test TC-03C – Login Using Email and Password (Successful Login)	64
5.12	Unit Test TC-04A – Password Recovery Using Forgot Password (Empty Email Field)	65
5.13	Unit Test TC-04B – Password Recovery Using Forgot Password (Invalid Email Format)	66

5.14	Unit Test TC-04C – Password Recovery Using Forgot Password (Unregistered Email)	67
5.15	Unit Test TC-04D – Password Recovery Using Forgot Password (Successful Password Reset Request)	68
5.16	Unit Test TC-05E – Password Recovery Using Forgot Password (Successful Password Reset and Login)	69
5.17	Unit Test TC-06A – Continue as a Guest (Guest Mode Access Without Logging In)	70
5.18	Unit Test TC-06B – Continue as a Guest (Attempt to Perform Restricted Actions)	71
5.19	Unit Test TC-06C – Continue as a Guest (Session Expiry on App Restart)	72
5.20	Unit Test TC-06D – Continue as a Guest (Upgrade to Full Account by Logging In or Signing Up)	73
5.21	Unit Test TC-07A – Create a Community (Empty Fields)	74
5.22	Unit Test TC-07B – Create a Community (Duplicate Community Name)	75
5.23	Unit Test TC-07C – Create a Community (Successful Community Creation)	76
5.24	Unit Test TC-08A – Join a Community (Attempt with No Internet Connection)	77
5.25	Unit Test TC-08B – Join a Community (Already a Member of the Community)	78
5.26	Unit Test TC-08C – Join a Community (Successful Community Join)	79
5.27	Unit Test TC-09A – Add a Post in a Community (Empty Post Submission)	80
5.28	Unit Test TC-09B – Add a Post in a Community (Exceeding Character Limit)	81
5.29	Unit Test TC-09C – Add a Post in a Community (Successful Text Post Creation)	82
5.30	Unit Test TC-09D – Add a Post in a Community (Successful Post with Media Attachment)	83
5.31	Unit Test TC-10A – Interact with a Post (Upvote Without Logging In)	84
5.32	Unit Test TC-10B – Interact with a Post (Downvote Without Logging In)	85
5.33	Unit Test TC-10C – Interact with a Post (Successful Upvote and Downvote by Logged-In User)	86
5.34	Unit Test TC-10D – Interact with a Post (Attempt to Submit Empty Comment)	87
5.35	Unit Test TC-10E – Interact with a Post (Successful Comment Submission by Logged-In User)	88
5.36	Unit Test TC-11A – Search for Communities (Empty Search Query)	89
5.37	Unit Test TC-11B – Search for Communities (Successful Search)	90
5.38	Unit Test TC-12A – Report a Post (As Guest User)	91

5.39	Unit Test TC-12B – Report a Post (Successful Report by Logged-In User)	92
5.40	Unit Test TC-13A – View Profile (As Guest User)	93
5.41	Unit Test TC-13B – View Profile (As Logged-In User)	94
5.42	Unit Test TC-13C – Edit Own Profile (Successful Update)	95
5.43	Unit Test TC-14A – Access Admin Panel (Unauthorized User Attempt)	96
5.44	Unit Test TC-14C – Approve Doctor Verification Request	97
5.45	Integration Test TP1 – User Authentication & Authorization	98
5.46	Integration Test TP2 – Community Management	99
5.47	Integration Test TP3 – Post Creation & Interaction	100
5.48	Integration Test TP4 – Search Functionality	101
5.49	Integration Test TP5 – Machine Learning Model Integration	102
5.50	Integration Test TP6 – Notifications System	104
5.51	Integration Test TP7 – User Profile and Verification	106
5.52	Integration Test TP8 – Admin Dashboard	108
5.53	Integration Test TP9 – Logout Functionality	109
5.54	System Test ST-01 – Sign-up using "Continue with Google"	111
5.55	System Test ST-02 – Sign-up using Email	112
5.56	System Test ST-03 – Sign-up Confirmation Email	113
5.57	System Test ST-04 – Login using Email and Password	114
5.58	System Test ST-05 – Recover Password using "Forgot Password"	115
5.59	System Test ST-06 – Continue as a Guest	116
5.60	System Test ST-07 – Create a Community	117
5.61	System Test ST-08 – Join a Community	118
5.62	System Test ST-09 – Add a Post in a Community	119
5.63	System Test ST-10 – Interact with a Post (Upvote, Downvote, and Comment)	120
5.64	System Test ST-11 – Search for a Post, User, or Community	121
5.65	System Test ST-12 – Interact with Machine Learning Models	122
5.66	System Test ST-13 – Receive Notifications for Posts and Community Activities	123
5.67	System Test ST-14 – Manage User Profile	124
5.68	System Test ST-15 – Doctor Verification Process	125
5.69	System Test ST-16 – Admin Dashboard for Doctor Verification	126
5.70	System Test ST-17 – Logout Functionality	127
5.71	Load Testing	129
5.72	Stress Testing – Estimated Load Time for Functionalities	130
5.73	Spike Testing – Estimated Load Time for Functionalities	131
5.74	Scalability Testing – System Behavior under Increased Load	132
5.75	Security Test ST-01 – Integrity Security Test Cases	133
5.76	Security Test ST-02 – Confidentiality Security Test Cases	134
5.77	Security Test ST-03 – Authentication Security Test Cases	135
5.78	Security Test ST-04 – Authorization Security Test Cases	136

5.79	Security Test ST-05 – Availability Security Test Cases	137
5.80	Security Test ST-06 – Non-Repudiation Security Test Cases	138
5.81	Usability Testing Table	139
5.82	Compatibility Testing Table	140
6.1	Model Performance Comparison	141
6.2	Performance Metrics of Deep Learning Models for Pneumonia De- tection	142

Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
ML	Machine Learning
DL	Deep Learning
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network
XAI	Explainable Artificial Intelligence
SHAP	SHapley Additive exPlanations
LIME	Local Interpretable Model-agnostic Explanations
AUC	Area Under the Curve
ROC	Receiver Operating Characteristic
RSNA	Radiological Society of North America
CDSS	Clinical Decision Support System
SVM	Support Vector Machine
RNN	Recurrent Neural Network
CT	Computed Tomography
MRI	Magnetic Resonance Imaging
PACS	Picture Archiving and Communication System
NLP	Natural Language Processing
NIH	National Institutes of Health
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit

Abstract

In the evolving landscape of healthcare, the exchange of knowledge among professionals is essential for quality patient care [1]. Traditional consultation methods are often time-consuming and inefficient. To address this, we propose Mualij, a doctor-to-doctor information-sharing platform modeled after Stack Overflow [2]. Mualij fosters collaborative knowledge sharing by enabling doctors to ask questions and receive peer responses. Additionally, the platform integrates AI models for disease prediction, currently focusing on heart failure and pneumonia detection, to assist in accurate decision-making. By combining seamless communication with AI-driven insights, Mualij aims to enhance professional collaboration and improve healthcare delivery.

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Introduction

The healthcare sector is continuously evolving, with technology playing an increasingly pivotal role in enhancing patient care and accessibility to medical services. The advent of digital platforms has revolutionized many aspects of healthcare, including patient management, diagnosis, and treatment planning. However, there remains a significant gap in the provision of platforms dedicated to professional interaction among doctors. Traditional methods of consultation and information exchange, such as in-person meetings, emails, and static databases, can be inefficient and time-consuming. To address these challenges, we propose the development of Mualij, a comprehensive Doctor-to-Doctor Information sharing System.

Mualij is designed to function as a dynamic, interactive platform where doctors can ask questions, share insights, and provide answers to their peers. This system draws inspiration from Stack Overflow, a widely used platform in the technology sector, known for its robust question-and-answer format. By adapting this model to the healthcare domain, Mualij aims to facilitate the seamless exchange of knowledge and expertise among doctors, fostering a collaborative environment that supports continuous learning and professional development.

At the core of Mualij provides heart disease(failure) prediction and pneumonia detection. Initially the system will only have support for heart disease(failure) prediction and pneumonia detection, and later on more diseases will be added. Cardiovascular diseases are among the leading causes of morbidity and mortality worldwide [3], making it imperative for doctors to have access to the latest and most accurate information. The AI component of Mualij leverages advanced machine learning algorithms to provide precise and relevant answers. This feature

ensures that doctors receive timely and reliable information, aiding them in their clinical decision-making processes.

The significance of Mualij lies in its potential to transform the way doctors interact and share knowledge. By providing a dedicated platform for professional collaboration, Mualij aims to overcome the limitations of traditional consultation methods. The system's user-friendly interface, empower doctors to seek advice, discuss complex cases, and stay updated with the latest advancements in their field. Furthermore, the platform's integration of features such as upvoting, commenting, and tagging will enhance the organization and accessibility of information, making it easier for doctors to find and contribute valuable insights.

Overall, this project sets out to address the fundamental challenges in professional interaction among doctors, with a focus on enhancing knowledge sharing and collaboration. By integrating AI technology and adopting a user-centric approach, Mualij aims to make a significant contribution to the healthcare industry's ongoing evolution.

1.2 Objectives

- Develop a user-friendly platform for doctors to ask and answer questions.
- Implement ML technology to make prediction related to heart disease(failure) and pneumonia detection.
- Facilitate professional collaboration and knowledge sharing among healthcare providers.
- Ensure the platform is secure and maintains the confidentiality of user interactions.
- Integrate features for upvoting, commenting, and tagging questions for better organization and accessibility.

1.3 Project Statement

To develop a Doctor-to-Doctor Information sharing System with integrated AI capabilities for predicting heart disease(failure) and pneumonia detection providing a platform for professional knowledge sharing and consultation among doctors.

1.4 Project Scope

- User registration and authentication for verified doctors.

- Question and answer functionality with tagging and categorization.
- AI-driven responses for heart disease(failure) prediction and pneumonia detection
- Upvote and comment features for community engagement.
- Real-time notification system.
- User profiles showcasing professional background and expertise.
- Advanced search functionality to find relevant questions and answers.
- Data encryption and privacy protection measures.

Chapter 2

Requirement Analysis

2.1 Literature Review

2.1.1 Heart Disease Prediction

In recent years, machine learning (ML) has emerged as a transformative approach in the field of predictive medicine, with a growing body of literature supporting its use for early detection and diagnosis of cardiovascular diseases (CVDs). Numerous algorithms have been employed to model the complex interplay of clinical and lifestyle factors that contribute to heart disease. Initial studies often relied on traditional linear classifiers such as logistic regression due to their simplicity, interpretability, and well-established use in medical research [4]. These models are particularly useful in clinical environments where transparency is essential and black-box decision-making may not be accepted without justification. However, the linearity assumption limits their ability to capture higher-order feature interactions, which are prevalent in biological systems.

As the volume and complexity of clinical data have increased, researchers have adopted more flexible algorithms capable of modeling nonlinear relationships. Support Vector Machines (SVMs) have been explored as an alternative to linear models, leveraging kernel tricks to project data into higher dimensional spaces and identify complex decision boundaries [5]. Though SVMs often outperform simpler models in terms of classification accuracy, their performance is sensitive to hyperparameter tuning and they are computationally intensive for large datasets. Decision trees, another commonly used model in medical diagnosis, are valued for their human-readable logic structure, but suffer from overfitting when used as standalone classifiers.

To overcome these challenges, ensemble learning methods such as Random Forest, Gradient Boosting, and Bagging have become the standard in many machine learning competitions and real-world applications. Random Forest, which aggregates predictions from multiple decision trees trained on bootstrapped subsets of the data, has demonstrated improved stability and predictive performance across a wide range of healthcare datasets [6]. Gradient Boosting Machines (GBMs), particularly XGBoost and LightGBM, offer even greater flexibility and efficiency by sequentially correcting the residuals of weak learners and applying regularization to prevent overfitting [7]. These methods have shown state-of-the-art performance in cardiovascular prediction tasks, outperforming traditional models in terms of both accuracy and generalization.

Despite the proliferation of studies applying these advanced models, many rely heavily on benchmark datasets such as the UCI Cleveland Heart Disease dataset. While these datasets provide a convenient starting point for algorithm development and comparison, they are often curated, balanced, and lack the noise typical of real-world clinical environments [4]. Models trained exclusively on such data may perform well in controlled conditions but fail to generalize to heterogeneous populations or incomplete datasets common in hospital records. Furthermore, these datasets typically consist of fewer than 1,000 records, which limits the ability of high-capacity models to learn meaningful representations without overfitting.

Another key challenge in the literature is the inconsistent application of preprocessing techniques and feature engineering practices. The choice of encoding schemes, handling of missing data, scaling methods, and outlier removal strategies significantly affect model performance and reproducibility. Some studies report high accuracies without detailing the preprocessing steps, making it difficult for others to replicate or validate findings. Raschka and Mirjalili [8] emphasize that robust preprocessing pipelines can often yield greater performance gains than merely switching between models. This observation highlights the critical need for transparency in methodological reporting, especially in clinical applications where decision-making must be both accountable and evidence based.

Beyond accuracy, recent literature increasingly acknowledges the importance of model interpretability, particularly in high-stakes domains such as healthcare. Many of the best-performing models—such as XGBoost, CatBoost, and neural networks—are inherently opaque, which poses challenges for clinical adoption. Explainable AI (XAI) methods, including SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations), LIME (Local Interpretable Model-agnostic Explanations), and counterfactual analysis have been proposed to fill this gap by attributing predictions to

specific input features [9]. These methods enable clinicians to verify that model predictions are based on medically reasonable factors, increasing trust and facilitating regulatory approval. Despite their growing importance, XAI methods are not yet routinely integrated into cardiovascular prediction pipelines, and few studies assess the alignment of feature attributions with clinical domain knowledge.

A relatively underexplored topic in the literature is the issue of model fairness and demographic bias. Very few studies investigate whether model performance varies across subgroups defined by age, gender, socioeconomic status, or ethnicity. This omission is concerning given that biased models may exacerbate existing health disparities. There is a growing recognition that fairness metrics should accompany traditional performance measures in health-focused ML studies, particularly when models are deployed in diverse and multiethnic populations. Without such analyses, models risk overfitting to majority groups in the training data while underperforming on minorities, thereby compromising their equity and safety in clinical use.

Recent studies have also examined the integration of machine learning models into clinical decision-support systems (CDSS). These systems are designed to assist clinicians by flagging high-risk patients during routine screenings, triaging patients based on risk scores, or providing second opinions on diagnostic assessments. Successful deployments of ML CDSS have been reported in domains such as radiology, pathology, and intensive care units. However, in the case of cardiovascular disease, most studies remain at the proof-of concept stage, and few have undergone real-world testing. Barriers include lack of clinician trust, data governance concerns, ethical implications, and uncertainty about how ML predictions should be acted upon in care pathways. The literature suggests that for machine learning systems to achieve widespread clinical adoption, they must be co-developed with healthcare professionals, rigorously validated across diverse clinical settings, and embedded into workflows in a manner that augments—rather than replaces—human expertise.

Finally, several meta-analyses have called for more comprehensive benchmarking studies using real-world datasets to evaluate how different algorithms perform under consistent evaluation criteria. Studies like those conducted by Caruana and Niculescu-Mizil [10] provide early examples of empirical comparisons across multiple models, but similar efforts are needed specifically within the cardiovascular domain. The present study addresses this need by evaluating both linear and ensemble classifiers on a large-scale, real world dataset with a reproducible pre-processing and evaluation pipeline. By situating model performance within the

context of data complexity, feature engineering, and interpretability, this study contributes a meaningful perspective to the evolving field of ML-driven cardiovascular risk prediction.

2.1.2 Pneumonia Detection

The use of artificial intelligence (AI) in medical imaging has undergone a rapid transformation over the past decade, with deep learning models playing a central role in diagnostic support tools. Convolutional neural networks (CNNs), in particular, have shown immense potential in learning complex visual features directly from medical images such as chest X-rays, CT scans, and MRIs. Unlike traditional computer vision methods that depend on hand-crafted features, CNNs are capable of learning hierarchical representations from raw pixel data, which makes them especially suitable for image classification tasks in radiology [11]. This capability has opened up new possibilities in disease detection, diagnosis assistance, and decision support systems in clinical practice.

One of the earliest large-scale efforts in automating chest X-ray interpretation came from the National Institutes of Health (NIH), which released the ChestX-ray14 dataset containing more than 100,000 frontal-view X-rays labeled with 14 different thoracic conditions [12]. This dataset became the foundation for many subsequent studies in chest disease classification. A landmark study based on this dataset was CheXNet, developed by Rajpurkar et al., which utilized a DenseNet121 architecture and claimed radiologist-level performance in detecting pneumonia [13]. Although the model demonstrated impressive accuracy, it relied on labels extracted using natural language processing (NLP) from radiology reports, which led to concerns about label accuracy and consistency. Furthermore, the multi-label nature of the dataset complicated binary classification tasks, as co-occurring conditions were common, and the labels were not always mutually exclusive. In contrast, the RSNA Pneumonia Detection Challenge dataset was specifically designed to address these limitations by focusing solely on pneumonia detection. Released in collaboration with the Radiological Society of North America (RSNA), this dataset includes over 26,000 chest X-ray images labeled by radiologists and reviewed for accuracy [14]. Each image is annotated as either normal or pneumonia-positive, providing a binary classification setup. The dataset also includes bounding box annotations to mark infected regions, although the present study uses only classification labels. The RSNA dataset has gained popularity due to its high-quality annotations and clinical relevance, making it suitable for model training and evaluation in real-world diagnostic scenarios.

In recent years, transfer learning has emerged as a dominant strategy in medical image classification. Instead of training models from scratch, which often requires large labeled datasets and extensive computational resources, transfer learning allows researchers to use pre-trained models—typically trained on ImageNet—and adapt them to specific medical tasks [15]. Models such as ResNet, EfficientNet, DenseNet, and Xception have been widely adopted in this domain. ResNet, introduced by He et al., introduced residual connections that allow for deeper networks without degradation in performance [16]. EfficientNet, developed by Google, uses a compound scaling method to uniformly scale depth, width, and resolution, resulting in models that are both accurate and computationally efficient [17]. DenseNet architectures are known for their densely connected layers that improve feature reuse and gradient flow [18], while Xception models use depthwise separable convolutions to reduce computational cost without sacrificing performance [19]. Many research efforts have explored the use of these architectures in pneumonia detection. Chouhan et al. compared multiple models including VGG16, ResNet, and DenseNet for pneumonia detection and reported that DenseNet121 achieved superior results in terms of AUC and F1-score [20]. Similarly, Islam et al. proposed a model ensemble combining various CNNs to improve diagnostic accuracy [21]. Although ensemble approaches can enhance performance, they often come at the cost of higher computational complexity and may not be practical for real time applications or deployment in low-resource settings. Other studies, such as those by Rahman et al. and Liang et al., have investigated the impact of input resolution, model depth, and training strategy on classification performance [22]. These findings emphasize the importance of careful model selection and pipeline consistency when developing reliable diagnostic tools.

However, despite these advances, many studies suffer from inconsistencies in pre-processing steps, evaluation criteria, and training pipelines. Some research uses grayscale images, while others convert them to RGB. Some employ heavy augmentation, while others use raw images. Evaluation metrics also vary, with some studies emphasizing accuracy, and others reporting only AUC or precision. These inconsistencies make it difficult to compare results across studies or replicate findings in other settings [23]. More importantly, in the context of pneumonia detection, metrics such as recall and AUC are often more clinically relevant than raw accuracy, as they reflect a model's ability to correctly detect positive cases while minimizing false negatives. Another critical but frequently overlooked issue is class imbalance. The RSNA dataset, like many clinical datasets, contains significantly more normal cases than pneumonia positive cases. Without proper class imbalance handling, models may become biased toward predicting the majority

class, resulting in high accuracy but poor sensitivity to actual pneumonia cases. Various strategies such as oversampling, under-sampling, and class weighting have been used to mitigate this issue. Among them, class weighting during training has proven to be a practical and effective method, particularly when dealing with medical images that are not easily augmented or resampled without introducing artifacts [22].

Despite the progress in developing pneumonia detection models, few studies have systematically compared multiple CNN-based architectures under a controlled and consistent experimental setup using the RSNA dataset. This gap limits the ability to identify which architectures are best suited for real-world deployment. Comparative studies are essential because different models vary in how they generalize to subtle image features, handle class imbalance, and respond to preprocessing pipelines. The current research aims to fill this gap by providing a side-by-side evaluation of several deep learning models using the same dataset, the same training validation split, the same preprocessing steps, and the same evaluation metrics. This approach ensures a fair comparison and yields insights into which architecture performs best under equal conditions. Ultimately, the need for reliable and reproducible models in clinical diagnostics has never been more urgent. Pneumonia continues to pose a serious health risk, and timely diagnosis can significantly impact treatment outcomes. Deep learning offers a promising solution, but only when applied with rigorous evaluation and a clear understanding of model behavior. The comparative approach adopted in this study not only helps identify the best performing architecture but also provides guidance for future research and clinical translation in pneumonia detection using chest X-rays. While prior studies have laid a strong foundation in applying deep learning to pneumonia detection, the need for consistent evaluation and direct model comparison remains critical. This research contributes by systematically analyzing multiple CNN-based models under a unified framework, offering clearer insights into their relative strengths and limitations. The findings aim to guide future efforts in selecting and deploying deep learning architectures for practical, reliable use in clinical settings.

2.2 Requirement Elicitation

2.2.1 Functional Requirements

In order to function fully, the capabilities, features, and behaviors exhibited by the system are termed as functional requirements. These requirements outline the complete functionality of the system describing what it should do and how it should behave in various scenarios.

The followings are the functional requirements in the context of our system:

- (FR-01-01): The system shall allow users to create post.
- (FR-01-02): The system shall allow users to sign up or login.
- (FR-01-03): The system shall be able to distinguish between Doctors and general users through verification.
- (FR-01-04): The system shall allow users to tag posts for categorization.
- (FR-01-05): The system shall allow users to interact with model that will predict heart disease(failure) prediction and pneumonia detection.
- (FR-01-06): The system shall allow the user to interact with post i.e upvote, downvote and comment.
- (FR-01-07): The system shall allow users to maintain their profile.
- (FR-01-08): The system shall allow user to search for their desired post/questions.

2.2.2 Non-Functional Requirements

Non-functional requirements specify how the system should do it. Non-functional requirements do not affect the basic functionality of the system report. The followings are non-functional requirements for our system

- Usability: The users must find it easy to work with the system, post questions and interaction with post. The system should be easy to navigate and user-friendly.
- Reliability / Availability: The system must be available 24/7 for the users.
- Scalability: The system must be designed to handle the growing number of users smoothly.
- Performance: The system must be able to load post in a reasonable time frame.
- Supportability: The system must be able to handle multiple user requests simultaneously.
- Security: The system must be able to handle personal data of users securely.

- Compatibility: The system must be compatible with different versions of android available.
- Robustness: The system must be able to process varying lengths posts.

2.3 Use Case Diagram

FIGURE 2.1: Use Case Diagram

2.4 Use Cases

Name	Sign In
Actors	User
Goals	Sign in to the app
Triggers	User requests to login
Pre-Condition	User should be registered or have a valid Google account
Post-Condition	User is logged into the system and gains access to functionalities like posting queries
Basic Flow	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. User opens the app 2. Enters email and password or chooses Google login 3. System authenticates the user 4. User is granted access
Alternative Flow	User must register before logging in if they don't have an account
Exceptions	Login fails if the user hasn't registered

TABLE 2.1: Use Case: Sign In

Name	Account Registration
Actors	User
Goals	Register a new account
Triggers	User requests to register an account
Pre-Condition	User has not already registered
Post-Condition	User account is successfully created
Basic Flow	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. User opens the app 2. Clicks Continue with Google or Sign-up 3. Selects Google account 4. Account is registered
Alternative Flow	None
Exceptions	Registration fails or user is not interested

TABLE 2.2: Use Case: Account Registration

Name	Create Post
Actors	User
Goals	Post created successfully
Triggers	User initiates a post creation
Pre-Condition	User is logged in and joined or created a community
Post-Condition	Post is visible in the community
Basic Flow	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. User joins or creates a community 2. Clicks "Create Post" 3. Adds description, image, and tags 4. Clicks "Post"
Alternative Flow	None
Exceptions	User is not registered or not logged in

TABLE 2.3: Use Case: Create Post

Name	Delete Post
Actors	User
Goals	Delete a previously posted post
Triggers	User initiates delete action on a post
Pre-Condition	User is logged in and is the author of the post
Post-Condition	Post is permanently removed
Basic Flow	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. User opens profile 2. Views post 3. Clicks "Delete Post"
Alternative Flow	None
Exceptions	Unauthorized deletion attempt

TABLE 2.4: Use Case: Delete Post

Name	Interact with Post
Actors	User
Goals	Upvote, downvote, or comment on a post
Triggers	User views a post
Pre-Condition	User is logged in and a member of the post's community
Post-Condition	Post interaction (reaction or comment) is updated
Basic Flow	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. User opens post 2. Clicks upvote/downvote or types a comment 3. Confirms interaction
Alternative Flow	None
Exceptions	Interaction fails or post doesn't load

TABLE 2.5: Use Case: Interact with Post

Name	AI Model Prediction
Actors	User
Goals	User gets predicted result successfully
Triggers	User requests AI model prediction
Pre-Condition	User is logged into the system
Post-Condition	System provides accurate prediction
Basic Flow	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. User clicks to open input page 2. Enters parameters 3. Clicks Predict 4. Results are displayed
Alternative Flow	None
Exceptions	User not registered or required fields left empty

TABLE 2.6: Use Case: AI Model Prediction

Name	Profile Management
Actors	User
Goals	Update and manage profile
Triggers	User opens profile settings
Pre-Condition	User is registered and logged in
Post-Condition	Profile is updated
Basic Flow	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Click profile icon 2. Click edit 3. Update details 4. Click update
Alternative Flow	None
Exceptions	Profile not loaded or required fields empty

TABLE 2.7: Use Case: Profile Management

Name	Search Post
Actors	User
Goals	Find relevant posts through search
Triggers	User inputs a search query
Pre-Condition	User is logged in
Post-Condition	Relevant results are shown
Basic Flow	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Click search button 2. Type search term 3. Click search 4. View results
Alternative Flow	None
Exceptions	Irrelevant results or network error

TABLE 2.8: Use Case: Search Post

Name	Create Community
Actors	User
Goals	Successfully create a community
Triggers	User clicks Create Community
Pre-Condition	User is logged in
Post-Condition	Community is created and user becomes moderator
Basic Flow	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Click "Create Community" 2. Enter name/details 3. Confirm creation
Alternative Flow	None
Exceptions	User is not registered

TABLE 2.9: Use Case: Create Community

Name	Edit Community
Actors	User
Goals	Modify community details
Triggers	User requests to edit their created community
Pre-Condition	User is logged in and owns the community
Post-Condition	Community info is updated
Basic Flow	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Visit community page 2. Click edit 3. Modify banner/description/moderators 4. Save changes
Alternative Flow	None
Exceptions	Unauthorized access or failed update

TABLE 2.10: Use Case: Edit Community

Name	Add Moderators
Actors	User
Goals	Add moderators to a community
Triggers	User clicks to add moderators
Pre-Condition	User is logged in and owns the community
Post-Condition	Selected moderators are assigned
Basic Flow	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Visit created community 2. Click "Edit Info" 3. Add/remove moderators 4. Click "Set Changes"
Alternative Flow	None
Exceptions	User is not logged in or not authorized

TABLE 2.11: Use Case: Add Moderators

Name	Join Community
Actors	User
Goals	Become a member of a community
Triggers	User clicks to join a community
Pre-Condition	User is registered and logged in
Post-Condition	User is a part of the selected community
Basic Flow	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Browse communities 2. Click "Join" on desired community 3. Confirm joining
Alternative Flow	None
Exceptions	User not logged in

TABLE 2.12: Use Case: Join Community

Name	Remove Post
Actors	Moderator
Goals	Remove a user's post from the community
Triggers	Moderator clicks remove on a flagged post
Pre-Condition	Moderator is logged in
Post-Condition	Post is removed with reason recorded
Basic Flow	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Moderator views post 2. Clicks "Remove Post" 3. Selects reason 4. Confirms action
Alternative Flow	None
Exceptions	Moderator not logged in or unauthorized

TABLE 2.13: Use Case: Remove Post

Name	Remove Community
Actors	Admin
Goals	Remove a community from the platform
Triggers	Admin clicks to remove community
Pre-Condition	Admin is logged in and authorized
Post-Condition	Community is deleted from platform
Basic Flow	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Admin views community 2. Clicks "Remove Community" 3. Enters reason 4. Clicks confirm
Alternative Flow	None
Exceptions	Community does not exist or admin not logged in

TABLE 2.14: Use Case: Remove Community

Chapter 3

System Design Analysis

3.1 Activity Diagrams

FIGURE 3.1: Login Activity Diagram

FIGURE 3.2: Account Registration Activity Diagram

FIGURE 3.3: Create Post Activity Diagram

FIGURE 3.4: Delete Post Activity Diagram

FIGURE 3.5: Interact with Post Activity Diagram

FIGURE 3.6: AI Model Prediction Activity Diagram

FIGURE 3.7: Profile Management Activity Diagram

FIGURE 3.8: Search Post Activity Diagram

FIGURE 3.9: Create Community Activity Diagram

FIGURE 3.10: Edit Community Activity Diagram

FIGURE 3.11: Add Moderators Activity Diagram

FIGURE 3.12: Join Community Activity Diagram

FIGURE 3.13: Award Post Activity Diagram

FIGURE 3.14: Remove Post Activity Diagram

FIGURE 3.15: Get Verified as Doctor Activity Diagram

3.2 Class Diagrams

FIGURE 3.16: Class Diagram

3.3 Sequence Diagrams

FIGURE 3.17: Login with Google Sequence Diagram

FIGURE 3.18: Login with email Sequence Diagram

FIGURE 3.19: Account Registration with Google Sequence Diagram

FIGURE 3.20: Account Registration with Email Sequence Diagram

FIGURE 3.21: Create Post Sequence Diagram

FIGURE 3.22: Delete Post Sequence Diagram

FIGURE 3.23: Interact with Post Sequence Diagram

FIGURE 3.24: AI Model Prediction Sequence Diagram

FIGURE 3.25: Profile Management Sequence Diagram

FIGURE 3.26: Search Post Sequence Diagram

FIGURE 3.27: Create Community Sequence Diagram

FIGURE 3.28: Edit Community Sequence Diagram

FIGURE 3.29: Add Moderators Sequence Diagram

FIGURE 3.30: Join Community Sequence Diagram

FIGURE 3.31: Award Post Sequence Diagram

FIGURE 3.32: Remove Post Sequence Diagram

FIGURE 3.33: Get Verified as Doctor Sequence Diagram

Chapter 4

System Implementation

4.1 Proposed Methodology

4.1.1 Heart Disease Prediction

The methodology adopted in this study was designed to rigorously evaluate the effectiveness of multiple machine learning classifiers for predicting cardiovascular disease using a real-world clinical dataset. The process involved a series of systematic steps that included initial model benchmarking, data preprocessing, model selection, training, hyperparameter optimization, and evaluation. Each stage was carried out using best practices in data science and was informed by both machine learning literature and clinical relevance to ensure the reliability and interpretability of the final results.

The first stage of the methodology consisted of an exploratory benchmark phase during which 18 different machine learning classifiers were initially trained and tested using the raw dataset without any preprocessing. This step was intended to serve as a baseline performance screen, providing insight into the general behavior and relative capabilities of a broad range of algorithms. Among the tested models were Decision Trees, Random Forests, Naive Bayes, K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), Support Vector Machines (SVM), AdaBoost, Gradient Boosting, and Multi-layer Perceptrons (MLPs). Evaluation at this stage relied primarily on training and testing accuracy, with particular attention paid to signs of overfitting, underfitting, or instability in model behavior. Models that demonstrated either severe overfitting (e.g., extremely high training accuracy with low test performance) or very poor generalization were excluded from further analysis.

Based on this initial evaluation, five classifiers were selected for in-depth experimentation: Logistic Regression, Ridge Classifier, Linear Support Vector Classifier (SVC), ExtraTrees Classifier, and XGBoost. This set of models was chosen to balance algorithmic diversity, represent both linear and non-linear approaches, and reflect a spectrum of interpretability and complexity. Logistic Regression and Ridge Classifier served as representative linear models. These are often favored in clinical settings due to their straightforward mathematical formulations and transparent coefficient outputs, which allow practitioners to understand the relative impact of each input feature. Linear SVC was included to capture the behavior of margin-based classifiers under linear constraints and was expected to perform well in high-dimensional feature spaces. ExtraTrees and XGBoost were included to evaluate ensemble tree-based methods, which have become standard for structured tabular data and are capable of modeling complex interactions between features.

All models were implemented in Python 3.10 using the Scikit-learn machine learning library (version 1.2.2) and the XGBoost open-source framework (version 1.7). Code execution and experiments were conducted on Google Colab's cloud-based runtime environment, which provided access to both CPU and GPU resources as needed. The environment was selected for its ease of collaboration, reproducibility, and compatibility with modern ML workflows. Where applicable, random seeds were fixed for each model to ensure consistent behavior across runs and to reduce variance in performance metrics during evaluation. Before training, the dataset was preprocessed following the pipeline described in the previous section. The cleaned and transformed dataset was divided into training and testing sets using an 80-20 stratified split to preserve the original class distribution in both subsets. Stratification was essential to ensure that both training and evaluation phases were not skewed by imbalances in disease prevalence, which could bias performance metrics and limit generalizability. Each model was trained on the training set and then evaluated on the testing set using a comprehensive set of classification metrics. Accuracy was used as the baseline indicator of overall performance, but it was complemented by precision, recall, F1-score, and area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUC-ROC). These additional metrics are particularly important in clinical applications, where the consequences of false positives and false negatives are asymmetrical. Recall, in particular, is crucial when the objective is to minimize the number of undiagnosed cases, while precision becomes important when trying to reduce unnecessary clinical interventions.

Hyperparameter tuning was performed for the two ensemble models—ExtraTrees

and XGBoost—using grid search with 5-fold cross-validation. For ExtraTrees, parameters such as the number of estimators (trees), maximum tree depth, and minimum samples required to split a node were systematically explored. For XGBoost, a wider array of hyperparameters was considered, including learning rate (eta), number of boosting rounds, maximum tree depth, L1 and L2 regularization (alpha, lambda), and the subsampling ratio. Grid search was chosen over random search due to the manageable parameter space and the interpretability of tuning outcomes. Each combination was evaluated using mean cross-validation accuracy, and the optimal parameters were selected based on the best average performance. The best configuration was then used to retrain the model on the entire training set for final testing.

In addition to performance evaluation, each model was assessed in terms of its interpretability and computational efficiency. Training time and prediction latency were recorded to understand the feasibility of deploying the models in real-time or near-real-time settings. Linear models, as expected, required minimal training time and produced instantaneous predictions, making them suitable for deployment in low-resource environments. Tree-based models, while more computationally intensive, offered the advantage of internal feature importance scoring and greater flexibility in modeling non-linearity and interactions. Feature importance was calculated using model-specific methods. For linear models, the absolute magnitude of standardized coefficients was used as a proxy for importance. For tree-based models, particularly XGBoost, built-in importance scores were extracted based on metrics such as gain and cover, which respectively indicate how much each feature contributed to reducing error and how often each feature was used for splitting. These insights were used to validate whether the models were prioritizing clinically relevant features, such as age, blood pressure, cholesterol, and BMI, in their decision-making processes.

The methodology also accounted for the possibility of model variance and instability by conducting multiple training and testing runs under different random splits. Standard deviation in accuracy, F1-score, and AUC was recorded to assess robustness. Models that exhibited high variance were flagged for further scrutiny, and their susceptibility to overfitting was analyzed. Finally, all results, parameters, and configurations were documented for reproducibility and version control, adhering to transparent machine learning practices recommended by the community.

Overall, this multi-stage methodology reflects a careful balance between model

complexity, interpretability, clinical relevance, and experimental rigor. By evaluating each model across a comprehensive suite of metrics and considering operational feasibility, the study provides a holistic view of the trade-offs involved in selecting machine learning algorithms for cardiovascular disease prediction in practical healthcare settings.

4.1.2 Pneumonia Detection

The methodology adopted in this study reflects a step-by-step approach to building, training, and comparing multiple deep learning models for pneumonia detection using chest X-ray images. The overall goal was to identify which convolutional neural network (CNN) architecture could deliver the most clinically useful performance, with a particular focus on recall and AUC, metrics critical in high-risk medical scenarios. The entire experimental process was conducted through the Kaggle platform, which offered GPU-based notebook environments for deep learning experimentation. Every model was implemented, trained, validated, and compared using the same dataset, same training-validation split, and identical pre-processing pipeline, ensuring a fair and controlled evaluation across architectures.

The research began by exploring publicly available medical imaging datasets through Kaggle. During this exploration, multiple datasets were considered, including the NIH ChestX-ray14 and the CheXpert dataset. While these datasets were large and well-known, they were not well-suited to the specific task of binary pneumonia classification due to their noisy, multi-label annotations. Labels were generated using natural language processing on radiology reports, introducing ambiguity and potential inconsistencies. This made it difficult to use them for precise, label-sensitive classification tasks like pneumonia detection, where true clinical supervision is critical.

Instead, the RSNA Pneumonia Detection Challenge dataset, also found through Kaggle, was selected due to its clear focus and high-quality annotations. Released as part of a collaborative challenge between the RSNA, SIIM, and ACR, this dataset contained over 26,000 chest X-ray images labeled as either “Pneumonia” or “Normal,” with a subset also containing bounding boxes indicating areas of infection. For the purposes of this study, only the image-level classification labels were used, and the task was limited to binary classification. This design simplified model evaluation and focused all efforts on the accuracy and sensitivity of pneumonia detection alone. The dataset’s reliable annotations, clinical relevance, and accessibility through Kaggle made it a strong foundation for the entire experimental pipeline.

The initial plan for model development involved experimenting with ensemble learning approaches. The motivation behind this was to combine the strengths of multiple CNN architectures and enhance overall performance by aggregating predictions through majority voting or averaging. However, during early trials on Kaggle, it became clear that training multiple large-scale models simultaneously was impractical. Kaggle’s session time limits and GPU memory constraints caused repeated disconnections, slow runtimes, and frequent interruptions, making it difficult to maintain stable progress across multiple models at once. Given these limitations, the ensemble plan was abandoned, and the study was restructured to focus on evaluating individual models through a standardized, iterative process.

The experiments began with the implementation of a custom CNN architecture developed from scratch. This model served as a baseline, helping verify the preprocessing pipeline and offering an initial understanding of how a lightweight model would perform on the RSNA dataset without any pre-trained knowledge. The custom CNN included several convolutional layers with ReLU activation functions, followed by max pooling and dense layers ending in a sigmoid output. While the model showed reasonable training behavior, it lacked the ability to generalize effectively, especially on validation data, highlighting the limitations of shallow architectures trained from scratch on relatively small medical datasets. To overcome these limitations, the study transitioned to transfer learning using pre-trained CNN models. The architectures selected included ResNet50, ResNet101, EfficientNetB0, EfficientNetB1, Xception, and DenseNet201. These models were chosen for their architectural diversity and proven performance in both general image classification tasks and medical imaging studies. Each model was initialized with weights pre-trained on ImageNet and modified to fit the pneumonia detection task. This involved removing the original classification layers and appending a custom head that included a global average pooling layer, dropout layers for regularization (typically set to 0.5), one or two dense layers, and a sigmoid activation unit for binary classification.

A two-phase training strategy was applied to all models. In the first phase, the pre-trained convolutional base of each model was frozen, and only the new classification layers were trained. This approach allowed the model to quickly adapt to the pneumonia classification task using the generalized features already learned from ImageNet. In the second phase, selected layers from the base model were unfrozen for fine tuning. Specifically, the last few blocks of layers (depending on the depth of the architecture) were made trainable. This unfreezing enabled the model to gradually re-learn features more relevant to chest X-rays while still retaining useful

low level image representations. For example, in DenseNet201, the final dense blocks and transition layers were unfrozen, whereas in ResNet101, layers from the fourth residual block onward were retrained. Fine-tuning was done using a lower learning rate, typically set between $1e-5$ and $1e-4$, to avoid destabilizing the pre-trained weights. Learning rates were adjusted manually based on early training observations to balance convergence speed with stability. In some models, such as ResNet50 and DenseNet201, reducing the learning rate after 3–5 epochs showed clear improvements in validation metrics. A learning rate scheduler was employed in several training cycles to dynamically reduce the learning rate on plateaus. The number of training epochs was typically kept to 10 in most experiments to avoid overfitting and due to runtime limitations on Kaggle. In cases where early stopping was applied, training was halted if the validation loss did not improve for five consecutive epochs.

The Adam optimizer was used across all models due to its ability to adapt learning rates for each parameter and its stability during gradient updates. Binary cross-entropy was chosen as the loss function, which is standard for binary classification tasks. Batch size was set to 16 in all cases, balancing memory usage and convergence efficiency. Each training run was monitored using validation loss and validation recall as primary indicators of model improvement. Input image pre-processing was customized for each architecture’s input size requirements. Images were resized to 224×224 pixels for models like ResNet and DenseNet, 240×240 for EfficientNetB1, and 299×299 for Xception. All images were originally grayscale but were expanded into 3-channel RGB format to match the expected input dimensions of ImageNet-trained models. Normalization was applied to scale pixel intensities to the $[0, 1]$ range. The class imbalance in the RSNA dataset was addressed by applying class weights during training. This weighting helped penalize incorrect predictions on pneumonia cases more heavily, thereby improving model sensitivity. Without class weighting, many models defaulted to favoring the majority “Normal” class, achieving high accuracy but poor recall.

The dataset was split using an 80:20 stratified division, ensuring that both training and validation subsets maintained the original class ratio. This step was crucial in maintaining consistency across experiments and ensuring that recall and AUC metrics were representative of real-world performance. No data augmentation techniques were applied in order to preserve a clean comparison across all models and ensure reproducibility.

Training and evaluation were performed entirely on Kaggle’s GPU-enabled notebooks. While this environment provided the advantage of free GPU access, it

also introduced constraints such as limited RAM, session timeouts, and automatic disconnections after inactivity. These constraints shaped the training schedule, prompting careful checkpoint saving and periodic reloading of model states. The `ModelCheckpoint` and `EarlyStopping` callbacks in Keras were used to automate model saving and training termination based on validation loss. Logs from training and validation runs were analyzed after each experiment to monitor convergence trends and evaluate overfitting behavior. Each model was evaluated using the same set of performance metrics: accuracy, recall, and area under the curve (AUC). While accuracy provided a general measure of classification correctness, recall was emphasized due to its importance in identifying actual pneumonia cases without missing critical diagnoses. AUC served as a comprehensive indicator of the model's discriminative power across all classification thresholds. These metrics, when viewed together, provided a reliable and clinically relevant assessment of model behavior.

Among all the architectures tested, `DenseNet201` consistently achieved the highest AUC and recall, demonstrating its strength in capturing subtle features in chest X-ray images. Its dense connectivity helped preserve gradient flow and feature reuse across layers, making it particularly well-suited for learning complex visual patterns related to pneumonia. The methodological choices—ranging from dataset selection to careful fine-tuning—contributed to building a robust experimental framework that produced both high-performing models and reproducible results suitable for further development in clinical AI systems.

4.2 Tools and Technologies

For the development of the `Mualij` application, a combination of modern and efficient tools has been selected. The primary integrated development environment (IDE) used is Visual Studio Code, known for its flexibility and rich extension ecosystem. On the front-end, Flutter is utilized for building a responsive and cross-platform user interface, while the back-end logic is implemented using Dart. For database services, Firebase is integrated to handle real-time data synchronization, authentication, and cloud storage, ensuring a robust and scalable infrastructure.

Chapter 5

System Testing and Evaluation

5.1 Unit Testing

Unit testing is a software testing approach that focuses on verifying individual functions, methods, or components in isolation. It ensures that each unit of code behaves as expected, making debugging easier, improving maintainability, and preventing regressions. Automated unit tests help developers detect errors early in the development cycle, leading to more reliable and efficient software.

In our Flutter application, unit testing plays a crucial role in validating core logic without relying on UI components. Using the `flutter_test` package, we can write tests to check the functionality of business logic, models, and services, ensuring a stable and scalable mobile application.

Test Case ID: TC-01A	Test Case Name: Signup Using “Continue with Google” (Empty Fields)
Test Case Description: Verify that signup fails if the user does not complete Google authentication.	Test Priority: High
Pre-Condition: <ul style="list-style-type: none">- The user is not logged in.- Active internet connection is available.- Google authentication is enabled.	Post-Condition: <ul style="list-style-type: none">- The user is not signed up.- An appropriate error message is displayed.

Sr. No.	Action	Expected Result	Actual Result	Status
1	Open the app and navigate to the signup screen.	The signup screen should display all signup options.	The signup options are visible.	Successful
2	Click on “Continue with Google.”	The Google authentication popup should appear.	The Google login prompt appears.	Successful
3	Close the Google authentication popup without selecting an account.	The system should cancel the authentication process.	The signup process is canceled.	Successful
4	Observe system behavior.	The user should remain on the signup screen with an error message.	The error message appears, preventing incomplete signup.	Successful

TABLE 5.1: Unit Test TC-01A – Signup Using “Continue with Google” (Empty Fields)

Test Case ID: TC-01B	Test Case Name: Signup Using “Continue with Google” (Incorrect Google Account)
Test Case Description: Verify that signup fails if an incorrect or restricted Google account is used.	Test Priority: High
Pre-Condition: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The user is not logged in. - Active internet connection is available. - Google authentication is enabled. 	Post-Condition: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The user is not signed up. - An appropriate error message is displayed.

Sr. No.	Action	Expected Result	Actual Result	Status
1	Open the app and navigate to the signup screen.	The signup screen should display all signup options.	The signup options are visible.	Successful
2	Click on “Continue with Google.”	The Google authentication popup should appear.	The Google login prompt appears.	Successful
3	Select a Google account that is disabled or restricted.	The system should reject authentication.	The authentication fails, and an error message appears.	Successful
4	Observe system behavior.	The user should remain on the signup screen with an error message.	The error message is displayed, preventing signup.	Successful

TABLE 5.2: Unit Test TC-01B – Signup Using “Continue with Google” (Incorrect Google Account)

Test Case ID: TC-01C	Test Case Name: Signup Using “Continue with Google” (Successful Signup)
Test Case Description: Verify that a user can successfully sign up using Google authentication.	Test Priority: High
Pre-Condition: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The user is not logged in. - Active internet connection is available. - Google authentication is enabled. 	Post-Condition: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The user account is created (if new). - The user is redirected to the home screen.

Sr. No.	Action	Expected Result	Actual Result	Status
1	Open the app and navigate to the signup screen.	The signup screen should display all signup options.	The signup options are visible.	Successful
2	Click on “Continue with Google.”	The Google authentication popup should appear.	The Google login prompt appears.	Successful
3	Select a valid Google account.	The system should authenticate and retrieve user details.	The authentication is successful, and user details are received.	Successful
4	The system processes the authentication response.	If the user is new, an account should be created.	A new account is created successfully.	Successful
5	The user is redirected to the home screen.	The user should be logged in and see the main interface.	The user lands on the home screen successfully.	Successful

TABLE 5.3: Unit Test TC-01C – Signup Using “Continue with Google” (Successful Signup)

Test Case ID: TC-02A	Test Case Name: Signup Using Email (Empty Fields)
Test Case Description: Verify that signup fails if all required fields are left empty.	Test Priority: High
Pre-Condition: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The user is not logged in. - Active internet connection is available. - The signup form is accessible. 	Post-Condition: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The user is not signed up. - Error messages appear for empty fields.

Sr. No.	Action	Expected Result	Actual Result	Status
1	Open the app and navigate to the signup screen.	The signup form should be displayed.	The signup screen is visible.	Successful
2	Click on the “Sign Up” button without entering any information.	The system should validate input and show errors for empty fields.	Error messages appear for required fields.	Successful
3	Observe system behavior.	The signup process should not proceed.	The user remains on the signup screen.	Successful

TABLE 5.4: Unit Test TC-02A – Signup Using Email (Empty Fields)

Test Case ID: TC-02B	Test Case Name: Signup Using Email (Invalid Email Format)
Test Case Description: Verify that signup fails if an invalid email format is entered.	Test Priority: High
Pre-Condition: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The user is not logged in. - Active internet connection is available. - The signup form is accessible. 	Post-Condition: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The user is not signed up. - Validation errors for incorrect email format are displayed.

Sr. No.	Action	Expected Result	Actual Result	Status
1	Open the app and navigate to the signup screen.	The signup form should be displayed.	The signup screen is visible.	Successful
2	Enter an incorrectly formatted email (e.g., missing @ or domain) and click Sign Up.	The system should display an error for invalid email format.	Validation error message is shown.	Successful
3	Observe system behavior.	The signup process should not proceed.	The user remains on the signup screen.	Successful

TABLE 5.5: Unit Test TC-02B – Signup Using Email (Invalid Email Format)

Test Case ID: TC-02C	Test Case Name: Signup Using Email (Weak Password)
Test Case Description: Verify that signup fails if the password entered is too weak.	Test Priority: High
Pre-Condition: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The user is not logged in. - Active internet connection is available. - The signup form is accessible. 	Post-Condition: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The user is not signed up. - An error is shown for weak password.

Sr. No.	Action	Expected Result	Actual Result	Status
1	Open the app and navigate to the signup screen.	The signup form should be displayed.	The signup screen is visible.	Successful
2	Enter a valid email but a weak password (e.g., "12345") and click Sign Up.	The system should reject the password and display a warning.	Weak password error is shown.	Successful
3	Observe system behavior.	The signup process should not proceed.	The user remains on the signup screen.	Successful

TABLE 5.6: Unit Test TC-02C – Signup Using Email (Weak Password)

Test Case ID: TC-02D	Test Case Name: Signup Using Email (Email Already Exists)
Test Case Description: Verify that signup fails if the entered email is already registered.	Test Priority: High
Pre-Condition: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The user is not logged in. - Active internet connection is available. - The signup form is accessible. 	Post-Condition: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The user is not signed up. - An error appears for existing account.

Sr. No.	Action	Expected Result	Actual Result	Status
1	Open the app and navigate to the signup screen.	The signup form should be displayed.	The signup screen is visible.	Successful
2	Enter an email already registered and click Sign Up.	The system should block signup and notify the user.	An error appears saying the email already exists.	Successful
3	Observe system behavior.	The signup process should not proceed.	The user remains on the signup screen.	Successful

TABLE 5.7: Unit Test TC-02D – Signup Using Email (Email Already Exists)

Test Case ID: TC-02E	Test Case Name: Signup Using Email (Successful Signup)
Test Case Description: Verify that a user can successfully sign up using a valid email and password.	Test Priority: High
Pre-Condition: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The user is not logged in. - Active internet connection is available. - The signup form is accessible. 	Post-Condition: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A new user account is created. - The user is redirected to the home screen.

Sr. No.	Action	Expected Result	Actual Result	Status
1	Open the app and navigate to the signup screen.	The signup form should be displayed.	The signup screen is visible.	Successful
2	Enter a valid email and strong password, then click Sign Up.	The user account should be created and the user redirected.	The account is created and home screen is shown.	Successful
3	Observe system behavior.	The user should be logged in.	The user is logged in successfully.	Successful

TABLE 5.8: Unit Test TC-02E – Signup Using Email (Successful Signup)

Test Case ID: TC-03A	Test Case Name: Login Using Email and Password (Empty Fields)
Test Case Description: Verify that login fails if both email and password fields are left empty.	Test Priority: High
Pre-Condition: - The user is on the login screen. - The user is not logged in.	Post-Condition: - The user is not logged in. - An error message is displayed.

Sr. No.	Action	Expected Result	Actual Result	Status
1	Open the app and navigate to the login screen.	The login screen should be displayed.	The login screen is visible.	Successful
2	Leave both fields empty and click Login.	The system should display validation errors.	Error messages for required fields are shown.	Successful
3	Observe system behavior.	Login should not proceed.	The user remains on the login screen.	Successful

TABLE 5.9: Unit Test TC-03A – Login Using Email and Password (Empty Fields)

Test Case ID: TC-03B	Test Case Name: Login Using Email and Password (Incorrect Credentials)
Test Case Description: Verify that login fails when incorrect credentials are provided.	Test Priority: High
Pre-Condition: - The user is not logged in. - The login screen is accessible.	Post-Condition: - Login attempt fails. - An appropriate error message is displayed.

Sr. No.	Action	Expected Result	Actual Result	Status
1	Open the app and navigate to the login screen.	The login screen should be displayed.	The login screen is visible.	Successful
2	Enter incorrect email/password and click Login.	The system should display an error.	Error message for incorrect credentials is shown.	Successful
3	Observe system behavior.	Login should not proceed.	The user remains on the login screen.	Successful

TABLE 5.10: Unit Test TC-03B – Login Using Email and Password (Incorrect Credentials)

Test Case ID: TC-03C	Test Case Name: Login Using Email and Password (Successful Login)
Test Case Description: Verify that the user can successfully log in using valid credentials.	Test Priority: High
Pre-Condition: - A valid account already exists. - The login screen is accessible.	Post-Condition: - The user is successfully logged in. - The home screen is displayed.

Sr. No.	Action	Expected Result	Actual Result	Status
1	Open the app and navigate to the login screen.	The login form should be displayed.	The login screen is visible.	Successful
2	Enter valid email and password, then click Login.	The user should be authenticated and redirected.	Login successful; redirected to home screen.	Successful
3	Observe system behavior.	The home screen should be shown.	The home screen is displayed.	Successful

TABLE 5.11: Unit Test TC-03C – Login Using Email and Password (Successful Login)

Test Case ID: TC-04A	Test Case Name: Password Recovery Using “Forgot Password” (Empty Email Field)
Test Case Description: Verify that password recovery fails if the email field is left empty.	Test Priority: High
Pre-Condition: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The user is on the password recovery screen. - The user is not logged in. 	Post-Condition: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The user is not sent a recovery link. - An error is displayed for empty field.

Sr. No.	Action	Expected Result	Actual Result	Status
1	Navigate to the “Forgot Password” screen.	The recovery form should be displayed.	Password recovery form is visible.	Successful
2	Leave the email field empty and click Submit.	The system should show a validation error.	Error message is shown.	Successful
3	Observe system behavior.	No recovery email should be sent.	No email is sent; error prevents submission.	Successful

TABLE 5.12: Unit Test TC-04A – Password Recovery Using “Forgot Password” (Empty Email Field)

Test Case ID: TC-04B	Test Case Name: Password Recovery Using “Forgot Password” (Invalid Email Format)
Test Case Description: Verify that password recovery fails if the email format is invalid.	Test Priority: High
Pre-Condition: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The user is on the password recovery screen. - The user is not logged in. 	Post-Condition: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No recovery email is sent. - Error shown for invalid format.

Sr. No.	Action	Expected Result	Actual Result	Status
1	Open the “Forgot Password” screen.	The form should be shown.	Form is visible.	Successful
2	Enter an invalid email format (e.g., “user@”) and click Submit.	System should reject the format and show an error.	Error message shown for invalid email.	Successful
3	Observe behavior.	No reset link should be sent.	No link sent; error displayed.	Successful

TABLE 5.13: Unit Test TC-04B – Password Recovery Using “Forgot Password” (Invalid Email Format)

Test Case ID: TC-04C	Test Case Name: Password Recovery Using “Forgot Password” (Unregistered Email)
Test Case Description: Verify that password recovery fails if the entered email is not registered.	Test Priority: High
Pre-Condition: - The user is not logged in. - Access to the password recovery screen.	Post-Condition: - No reset link is sent. - Error shown for unregistered email.

Sr. No.	Action	Expected Result	Actual Result	Status
1	Open the “Forgot Password” screen.	Password recovery form should load.	Recovery form is displayed.	Successful
2	Enter an unregistered email address and submit.	System should notify that the email is not found.	Error message shown for unregistered email.	Successful
3	Observe system behavior.	No recovery email should be sent.	No reset email sent.	Successful

TABLE 5.14: Unit Test TC-04C – Password Recovery Using “Forgot Password” (Unregistered Email)

Test Case ID: TC-04D	Test Case Name: Password Recovery Using “Forgot Password” (Successful Password Reset Request)
Test Case Description: Verify that a valid password reset request is processed successfully.	Test Priority: High
Pre-Condition: - The user is not logged in. - A registered email address exists.	Post-Condition: - Password reset email is sent. - User is notified.

Sr. No.	Action	Expected Result	Actual Result	Status
1	Open the “Forgot Password” screen.	Form loads correctly.	Recovery screen is shown.	Successful
2	Enter a valid registered email and submit.	System sends a password reset link.	Reset email is sent successfully.	Successful
3	Observe system behavior.	User is notified to check their inbox.	Notification shown; email sent.	Successful

TABLE 5.15: Unit Test TC-04D – Password Recovery Using “Forgot Password” (Successful Password Reset Request)

Test Case ID: TC-05E	Test Case Name: Password Recovery Using “Forgot Password” (Successful Password Reset and Login)
Test Case Description: Verify that a user can reset their password and log in successfully.	Test Priority: High
Pre-Condition: - The user has received a password reset email. - The password reset link is valid.	Post-Condition: - The user can log in with the new password.

Sr. No.	Action	Expected Result	Actual Result	Status
1	Open the email and click on the password reset link.	The system should redirect the user to a reset password page.	The password reset page loads.	Successful
2	Enter a new valid password and confirm it.	The system should validate and update the password.	The password is updated successfully.	Successful
3	Navigate to the login screen and enter the new password.	The system should authenticate the user and allow login.	The user logs in successfully.	Successful

TABLE 5.16: Unit Test TC-05E – Password Recovery Using “Forgot Password” (Successful Password Reset and Login)

Test Case ID: TC-06A	Test Case Name: Continue as a Guest (Guest Mode Access Without Logging In)
Test Case Description: Verify that a user can access the app as a guest and browse public content.	Test Priority: Medium
Pre-Condition: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The application is installed and launched. - The ”Continue as a Guest” feature is enabled. 	Post-Condition: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The user gains access as a guest. - Restricted actions remain unavailable without login.

Sr. No.	Action	Expected Result	Actual Result	Status
1	Open the app and navigate to the login/signup screen.	The login/signup interface should appear with a "Continue as a Guest" option.	The screen loads with the guest option available.	Successful
2	Click on "Continue as a Guest."	The system should bypass login and grant guest access.	Guest access is enabled without authentication.	Successful
3	Browse available public content.	The user can navigate and view posts, communities, and profiles.	Public content is accessible without restrictions.	Successful

TABLE 5.17: Unit Test TC-06A – Continue as a Guest (Guest Mode Access Without Logging In)

Test Case ID: TC-06B	Test Case Name: Continue as a Guest (Attempt to Perform Restricted Actions)
Test Case Description: Verify that guests cannot perform actions that require authentication.	Test Priority: High
Pre-Condition: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The user is accessing the app as a guest. - The system has defined restrictions for guest users. 	Post-Condition: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The user is blocked from restricted actions. - A login/signup prompt is displayed.

Sr. No.	Action	Expected Result	Actual Result	Status
1	Open the app and continue as a guest.	The user should be able to browse publicly available content.	Guest access is granted.	Successful
2	Attempt to create a post in a community.	The system should prevent posting and display a login/signup prompt.	A login prompt appears when posting is attempted.	Successful
3	Attempt to comment on a post.	The system should prevent commenting and request login/signup.	A login prompt appears when commenting is attempted.	Successful
4	Attempt to join a community.	The system should restrict joining communities and prompt for authentication.	The user is asked to log in before joining.	Successful

TABLE 5.18: Unit Test TC-06B – Continue as a Guest (Attempt to Perform Restricted Actions)

Test Case ID: TC-06C	Test Case Name: Continue as a Guest (Session Expiry on App Restart)
Test Case Description: Verify that the guest session does not persist after closing and reopening the app.	Test Priority: Medium
Pre-Condition: - The user is accessing the app as a guest.	Post-Condition: - The guest session is reset upon app restart. - The user must reselect "Continue as a Guest" or log in.

Sr. No.	Action	Expected Result	Actual Result	Status
1	Open the app and continue as a guest.	The user should be able to browse publicly available content.	Guest access is granted.	Successful
2	Exit the app completely.	The app session should be cleared.	The session is reset upon closing the app.	Successful
3	Reopen the app.	The system should return to the login/signup screen, requiring re-selection.	The user must re-select guest mode or log in.	Successful

TABLE 5.19: Unit Test TC-06C – Continue as a Guest (Session Expiry on App Restart)

Test Case ID: TC-06D	Test Case Name: Continue as a Guest (Upgrade to Full Account by Logging In or Signing Up)
Test Case Description: Verify that a guest user can log in or sign up to gain full account access.	Test Priority: High
Pre-Condition: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The user is accessing the app as a guest. - The login and signup options are available. 	Post-Condition: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The user successfully logs in or signs up. - The guest session is upgraded to a full account.

Sr. No.	Action	Expected Result	Actual Result	Status
1	Open the app and continue as a guest.	The user should be able to browse publicly available content.	Guest access is granted.	Successful
2	Navigate to the login/signup screen.	The system should provide options for login and signup.	The login/signup screen appears.	Successful
3	Enter valid credentials for login or signup.	The system should authenticate the user and grant full access.	The user is authenticated successfully.	Successful
4	Observe system behavior.	The user should have full access to all app features after login/signup.	The guest session is upgraded to a full account.	Successful

TABLE 5.20: Unit Test TC-06D – Continue as a Guest (Upgrade to Full Account by Logging In or Signing Up)

Test Case ID: TC-07A	Test Case Name: Create a Community (Empty Fields)
Test Case Description: Verify that a community cannot be created if required fields are left empty.	Test Priority: High
Pre-Condition: - The user is logged in. - The "Create Community" feature is enabled.	Post-Condition: - The community is not created. - An error message is displayed for missing required fields.

Sr. No.	Action	Expected Result	Actual Result	Status
1	Open the app and navigate to the "Create Community" section.	The system should display the community creation form.	The form appears successfully.	Successful
2	Click on "Create" without entering any information.	The system should validate the inputs and display error messages.	Error messages appear for empty fields.	Successful
3	Observe system behavior.	The community creation process should not proceed.	The user remains on the form.	Successful

TABLE 5.21: Unit Test TC-07A – Create a Community (Empty Fields)

Test Case ID: TC-07B	Test Case Name: Create a Community (Duplicate Community Name)
Test Case Description: Verify that a community cannot be created with a name that is already taken.	Test Priority: High
Pre-Condition: - The user is logged in. - At least one community already exists with the same name.	Post-Condition: - The community is not created. - An error message appears indicating a duplicate community name.

Sr. No.	Action	Expected Result	Actual Result	Status
1	Open the app and navigate to the "Create Community" section.	The system should display the community creation form.	The form appears successfully.	Successful
2	Enter a community name that already exists.	The system should check for duplicate names.	The system detects a duplicate name.	Successful
3	Click on "Create."	The system should prevent creation and display an error message.	The error message appears for duplicate names.	Successful
4	Observe system behavior.	The community creation process should not proceed.	The user remains on the form.	Successful

TABLE 5.22: Unit Test TC-07B – Create a Community (Duplicate Community Name)

Test Case ID: TC-07C	Test Case Name: Create a Community (Successful Community Creation)
Test Case Description: Verify that a user can successfully create a new community with valid details.	Test Priority: High
Pre-Condition: - The user is logged in. - The "Create Community" feature is enabled.	Post-Condition: - The community is created successfully. - The new community appears in the list of available communities.

Sr. No.	Action	Expected Result	Actual Result	Status
1	Open the app and navigate to the "Create Community" section.	The system should display the community creation form.	The form appears successfully.	Successful
2	Enter a unique community name and a valid description.	The system should accept and validate the input.	The input is valid.	Successful
3	Click on "Create."	The system should register and store the new community.	The community is created successfully.	Successful
4	Navigate to the list of communities.	The newly created community should be visible.	The new community appears in the list.	Successful

TABLE 5.23: Unit Test TC-07C – Create a Community (Successful Community Creation)

Test Case ID: TC-08A	Test Case Name: Join a Community (Attempt with No Internet Connection)
Test Case Description: Verify that a user cannot join a community without an active internet connection.	Test Priority: High
Pre-Condition: - The user is logged in. - The internet connection is disabled.	Post-Condition: - The user is not added to the community. - An error message appears indicating no internet connection.

Sr. No.	Action	Expected Result	Actual Result	Status
1	Open the app and navigate to the list of communities.	The community list should be displayed.	The list is visible.	Successful
2	Disable the internet connection.	The system should recognize that the user is offline.	The system detects no internet.	Successful
3	Click on the "Join" button for a community.	The system should prevent the action and display an error.	An error message appears indicating no internet.	Successful
4	Observe system behavior.	The user is not added to the community.	The join request is blocked.	Successful

TABLE 5.24: Unit Test TC-08A – Join a Community (Attempt with No Internet Connection)

Test Case ID: TC-08B	Test Case Name: Join a Community (Already a Member of the Community)
Test Case Description: Verify that a user cannot rejoin a community they are already a member of.	Test Priority: Medium
Pre-Condition: - The user is logged in. - The user is already a member of the community.	Post-Condition: - The user remains a member of the community. - An error message appears indicating duplicate membership.

Sr. No.	Action	Expected Result	Actual Result	Status
1	Open the app and navigate to a community the user has already joined.	The system should indicate that the user is a member.	The membership status is displayed.	Successful
2	Click on the "Join" button again.	The system should prevent the action and display a message.	An error message appears for duplicate membership.	Successful
3	Observe system behavior.	The user remains a member with no changes.	The system blocks duplicate joining.	Successful

TABLE 5.25: Unit Test TC-08B – Join a Community (Already a Member of the Community)

Test Case ID: TC-08C	Test Case Name: Join a Community (Successful Community Join)
Test Case Description: Verify that a user can successfully join a community.	Test Priority: High
Pre-Condition: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The user is logged in. - The user is not a member of the selected community. 	Post-Condition: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The user is added as a member of the community. - The system updates the user's membership status.

Sr. No.	Action	Expected Result	Actual Result	Status
1	Open the app and navigate to the list of communities.	The system should display all available communities.	The list is visible.	Successful
2	Select a community and click the "Join" button.	The system should process the request.	The system processes the join request.	Successful
3	The system checks if the user is already a member.	If the user is not a member, the request proceeds.	The membership status is verified.	Successful
4	The user is added to the community.	The user should now be listed as a community member.	The user's membership is updated.	Successful
5	Refresh the community page.	The "Join" button should now indicate "Member."	The membership status is updated successfully.	Successful

TABLE 5.26: Unit Test TC-08C – Join a Community (Successful Community Join)

Test Case ID: TC-09A	Test Case Name: Add a Post in a Community (Empty Post Submission)
Test Case Description: Verify that a post cannot be created if no content is entered.	Test Priority: High
Pre-Condition: - The user is logged in. - The user is a member of the community.	Post-Condition: - The post is not created. - An error message is displayed for missing content.

Sr. No.	Action	Expected Result	Actual Result	Status
1	Open the app and navigate to a joined community.	The system should display all available posts.	The community page loads successfully.	Successful
2	Click on the "Create Post" button.	The system should display the post creation interface.	The post creation screen appears.	Successful
3	Click on "Post" without entering any content.	The system should validate input and display an error message.	An error message appears for empty content.	Successful
4	Observe system behavior.	The post should not be created.	The post creation process is blocked.	Successful

TABLE 5.27: Unit Test TC-09A – Add a Post in a Community (Empty Post Submission)

Test Case ID: TC-09B	Test Case Name: Add a Post in a Community (Exceeding Character Limit)
Test Case Description: Verify that a post cannot exceed the maximum character limit.	Test Priority: Medium
Pre-Condition: - The user is logged in. - The user is a member of the community.	Post-Condition: - The post is not created. - An error message is displayed for exceeding the character limit.

Sr. No.	Action	Expected Result	Actual Result	Status
1	Open the app and navigate to a joined community.	The system should display all available posts.	The community page loads successfully.	Successful
2	Click on the "Create Post" button.	The system should display the post creation interface.	The post creation screen appears.	Successful
3	Enter text that exceeds the maximum character limit.	The system should prevent further input after reaching the limit.	The character limit is enforced.	Successful
4	Click on "Post."	The system should prevent submission and show an error message.	The error message appears for exceeding character limit.	Successful

TABLE 5.28: Unit Test TC-09B – Add a Post in a Community (Exceeding Character Limit)

Test Case ID: TC-09C	Test Case Name: Add a Post in a Community (Successful Text Post Creation)
Test Case Description: Verify that a user can successfully create a post with text content.	Test Priority: High
Pre-Condition: - The user is logged in. - The user is a member of the community.	Post-Condition: - The post is successfully created. - The post appears in the community feed.

Sr. No.	Action	Expected Result	Actual Result	Status
1	Open the app and navigate to a joined community.	The system should display all available posts.	The community page loads successfully.	Successful
2	Click on the "Create Post" button.	The system should display the post creation interface.	The post creation screen appears.	Successful
3	Enter valid text content in the input field.	The system should accept the content.	The content is entered successfully.	Successful
4	Click on "Post."	The system should create and publish the post.	The post is created and visible in the feed.	Successful

TABLE 5.29: Unit Test TC-09C – Add a Post in a Community (Successful Text Post Creation)

Test Case ID: TC-09D	Test Case Name: Add a Post in a Community (Successful Post with Media Attachment)
Test Case Description: Verify that a user can successfully create a post with media attachments such as images or videos.	Test Priority: High
Pre-Condition: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The user is logged in. - The user is a member of the community. - The app has media access permissions. 	Post-Condition: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The post is successfully created. - The post with media appears in the community feed.

Sr. No.	Action	Expected Result	Actual Result	Status
1	Open the app and navigate to a joined community.	The system should display all available posts.	The community page loads successfully.	Successful
2	Click on the "Create Post" button.	The system should display the post creation interface.	The post creation screen appears.	Successful
3	Enter valid text content and attach a media file (image/video).	The system should preview the media and validate both inputs.	The content and media are validated.	Successful
4	Click on "Post."	The system should publish the post with the attached media.	The post appears in the feed with media displayed.	Successful

TABLE 5.30: Unit Test TC-09D – Add a Post in a Community (Successful Post with Media Attachment)

Test Case ID: TC-10A	Test Case Name: Interact with a Post (Upvote Without Logging In)
Test Case Description: Verify that a non-logged-in user cannot upvote a post and is prompted to log in.	Test Priority: Medium
Pre-Condition: - The user is not logged in. - The post is visible on the feed.	Post-Condition: - The user is not allowed to upvote. - A login prompt is displayed.

Sr. No.	Action	Expected Result	Actual Result	Status
1	Open the app without logging in and navigate to a post.	The post should be visible for viewing.	The post is displayed on the feed.	Successful
2	Attempt to upvote the post.	The system should block the action and display a login prompt.	A login prompt appears preventing the upvote.	Successful
3	Observe system behavior.	No vote should be registered, and the user should remain on the post view.	No vote is recorded without login.	Successful

TABLE 5.31: Unit Test TC-10A – Interact with a Post (Upvote Without Logging In)

Test Case ID: TC-10B	Test Case Name: Interact with a Post (Downvote Without Logging In)
Test Case Description: Verify that a non-logged-in user cannot downvote a post and is prompted to log in.	Test Priority: Medium
Pre-Condition: - The user is not logged in. - The post is visible on the feed.	Post-Condition: - The user is not allowed to downvote. - A login prompt is displayed.

Sr. No.	Action	Expected Result	Actual Result	Status
1	Open the app without logging in and navigate to a post.	The post should be visible for viewing.	The post is displayed on the feed.	Successful
2	Attempt to downvote the post.	The system should block the action and display a login prompt.	A login prompt appears preventing the downvote.	Successful
3	Observe system behavior.	No vote should be registered, and the user should remain on the post view.	No vote is recorded without login.	Successful

TABLE 5.32: Unit Test TC-10B – Interact with a Post (Downvote Without Logging In)

Test Case ID: TC-10C	Test Case Name: Interact with a Post (Successful Upvote and Downvote by Logged-In User)
Test Case Description: Verify that a logged-in user can successfully upvote and downvote a post.	Test Priority: High
Pre-Condition: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The user is logged in. - A post is visible in the feed. 	Post-Condition: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The vote is registered. - The post reflects the updated vote count.

Sr. No.	Action	Expected Result	Actual Result	Status
1	Log in to the app and navigate to a visible post.	The post should be displayed with voting options.	The post is loaded successfully.	Successful
2	Click on the upvote icon.	The post's vote count should increment by 1.	The vote count increases.	Successful
3	Click on the downvote icon.	The post's vote count should decrement accordingly.	The vote count decreases.	Successful
4	Observe system behavior.	The post accurately reflects the voting action.	The votes are updated in real-time.	Successful

TABLE 5.33: Unit Test TC-10C – Interact with a Post (Successful Upvote and Downvote by Logged-In User)

Test Case ID: TC-10D	Test Case Name: Interact with a Post (Attempt to Submit Empty Comment)
Test Case Description: Verify that the system prevents submission of empty comments and prompts the user with an error.	Test Priority: High
Pre-Condition: - The user is logged in. - The post is visible in the feed.	Post-Condition: - The empty comment is not submitted. - An error message is displayed.

Sr. No.	Action	Expected Result	Actual Result	Status
1	Log in and open the app to view a post.	The post and comment input field should be visible.	The comment field appears.	Successful
2	Leave the comment field empty and click "Post Comment."	The system should prevent submission and display an error message.	An error message appears.	Successful
3	Observe system behavior.	The empty comment is not submitted.	The comment field remains unchanged.	Successful

TABLE 5.34: Unit Test TC-10D – Interact with a Post (Attempt to Submit Empty Comment)

Test Case ID: TC-10E	Test Case Name: Interact with a Post (Successful Comment Submission by Logged-In User)
Test Case Description: Verify that a logged-in user can successfully submit a comment on a post.	Test Priority: High
Pre-Condition: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The user is logged in. - A post is visible on the feed. 	Post-Condition: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The comment is submitted and visible under the post. - The input field is cleared.

Sr. No.	Action	Expected Result	Actual Result	Status
1	Log in and open the app to view a post.	The post and comment field should be visible.	The post appears with the comment input.	Successful
2	Enter valid text in the comment field.	The system should allow the input.	The comment is entered successfully.	Successful
3	Click "Post Comment."	The comment should be submitted and appear below the post.	The comment appears instantly.	Successful
4	Observe the field.	The input field should be cleared after submission.	The field resets after submission.	Successful

TABLE 5.35: Unit Test TC-10E – Interact with a Post (Successful Comment Submission by Logged-In User)

Test Case ID: TC-11A	Test Case Name: Search for Communities (Empty Search Query)
Test Case Description: Verify that the system handles empty search queries appropriately without returning results or crashing.	Test Priority: Medium
Pre-Condition: - The user is logged in. - The "Search Communities" feature is accessible.	Post-Condition: - No search results are displayed. - The system remains stable.

Sr. No.	Action	Expected Result	Actual Result	Status
1	Open the app and go to the community search interface.	The system should show the search input field.	The search screen loads properly.	Successful
2	Leave the search field empty and press enter/search.	The system should not perform the search and show a message or no results.	No results are returned, system remains idle.	Successful
3	Observe the system behavior.	The app should not crash or return invalid data.	The system handles the empty input gracefully.	Successful

TABLE 5.36: Unit Test TC-11A – Search for Communities (Empty Search Query)

Test Case ID: TC-11B	Test Case Name: Search for Communities (Successful Search)
Test Case Description: Verify that the user can successfully search for a community using valid keywords.	Test Priority: High
Pre-Condition: - The user is logged in. - The "Search Communities" feature is accessible.	Post-Condition: - The system returns a list of relevant communities. - The search results are displayed accurately.

Sr. No.	Action	Expected Result	Actual Result	Status
1	Open the app and navigate to the community search interface.	The search input field should be visible.	The field appears.	Successful
2	Enter a valid keyword related to an existing community.	The system should search based on the input.	The query is processed.	Successful
3	Review the list of search results.	Matching communities should be displayed.	Relevant communities are listed.	Successful
4	Select one of the listed communities.	The user should be navigated to the selected community's page.	The community page opens successfully.	Successful

TABLE 5.37: Unit Test TC-11B – Search for Communities (Successful Search)

Test Case ID: TC-12A	Test Case Name: Report a Post (As Guest User)
Test Case Description: Verify that guest users are restricted from reporting posts and prompted to log in.	Test Priority: Medium
Pre-Condition: - The user is not logged in. - The post is visible in the feed.	Post-Condition: - The report action is not processed. - The user is prompted to log in.

Sr. No.	Action	Expected Result	Actual Result	Status
1	Open the app without logging in and navigate to a visible post.	The post should be viewable to guests.	The post is visible.	Successful
2	Click on the "Report" icon or option.	The system should prevent the action and display a login prompt.	A login prompt appears.	Successful
3	Attempt to proceed with reporting.	The report should not be allowed until the user logs in.	The system blocks guest reports.	Successful

TABLE 5.38: Unit Test TC-12A – Report a Post (As Guest User)

Test Case ID: TC-12B	Test Case Name: Report a Post (Successful Report by Logged-In User)
Test Case Description: Verify that a logged-in user can successfully report a post and that the report is submitted to the system.	Test Priority: High
Pre-Condition: - The user is logged in. - The post is visible in the feed.	Post-Condition: - The post is reported successfully. - The report is submitted to the moderation system.

Sr. No.	Action	Expected Result	Actual Result	Status
1	Log in to the app and navigate to a visible post.	The post should be viewable with interactive options.	The post is displayed with report option.	Successful
2	Click on the "Report" icon.	A dialog or form should appear to choose the report reason.	The report interface appears.	Successful
3	Select a valid report reason and submit.	The system should accept the report and show confirmation.	Report is submitted with confirmation message.	Successful
4	Observe the system behavior.	The report is logged and sent to moderators/admin panel.	Report is recorded in the system.	Successful

TABLE 5.39: Unit Test TC-12B – Report a Post (Successful Report by Logged-In User)

Test Case ID: TC-13A	Test Case Name: View Profile (As Guest User)
Test Case Description: Verify that a guest user can view public profiles but with restricted access to certain actions or sections.	Test Priority: Medium
Pre-Condition: - The user is not logged in. - Public profiles are accessible to guests.	Post-Condition: - The guest user views the profile with limited access. - Restricted actions are unavailable.

Sr. No.	Action	Expected Result	Actual Result	Status
1	Open the app without logging in.	The guest mode should be activated.	Guest access is enabled.	Successful
2	Navigate to a user's profile from a post or comment.	The profile should be visible with limited information.	The public profile is shown.	Successful
3	Try to access restricted actions (e.g., follow, message, edit).	The system should block these actions and prompt for login.	Actions are disabled or redirect to login.	Successful

TABLE 5.40: Unit Test TC-13A – View Profile (As Guest User)

Test Case ID: TC-13B	Test Case Name: View Profile (As Logged-In User)
Test Case Description: Verify that a logged-in user can view their own and others' profiles with full access to available actions.	Test Priority: High
Pre-Condition: - The user is logged in. - Profiles are publicly accessible within the app.	Post-Condition: - The user can view and interact with profiles. - All permitted actions are available.

Sr. No.	Action	Expected Result	Actual Result	Status
1	Log in to the app.	The dashboard or home feed should be accessible.	User is logged in successfully.	Successful
2	Navigate to a user profile (own or another user).	The profile should be displayed with all public info.	Profile details appear correctly.	Successful
3	Try available actions like follow, message, view posts.	All enabled actions should be functional.	Actions work as expected.	Successful

TABLE 5.41: Unit Test TC-13B – View Profile (As Logged-In User)

Test Case ID: TC-13C	Test Case Name: Edit Own Profile (Successful Update)
Test Case Description: Verify that a logged-in user can successfully update their own profile information.	Test Priority: High
Pre-Condition: - The user is logged in. - The user has access to the profile editing interface.	Post-Condition: - The profile is updated successfully. - The changes are reflected immediately.

Sr. No.	Action	Expected Result	Actual Result	Status
1	Log in to the app and navigate to the profile section.	The user's profile should be displayed with an edit option.	Profile is visible with edit button.	Successful
2	Click the "Edit Profile" button.	The profile editing form should appear.	Edit form is shown.	Successful
3	Modify profile details (e.g., name, bio, profile picture).	The form should accept valid inputs.	Fields are updated with new values.	Successful
4	Save the changes.	The system should update the profile and show a success message.	Profile is updated and confirmed.	Successful
5	Refresh or revisit the profile.	The updated details should be visible.	New info appears correctly.	Successful

TABLE 5.42: Unit Test TC-13C – Edit Own Profile (Successful Update)

Test Case ID: TC-14A	Test Case Name: Access Admin Panel (Unauthorized User Attempt)
Test Case Description: Verify that non-admin users are restricted from accessing the admin panel and shown an error or redirected.	Test Priority: High
Pre-Condition: - The user is logged in. - The user does not have admin privileges.	Post-Condition: - Access to the admin panel is denied. - The user is redirected or shown an error message.

Sr. No.	Action	Expected Result	Actual Result	Status
1	Log in as a regular (non-admin) user.	The user is authenticated and directed to the home screen.	Logged in successfully.	Successful
2	Try to access the admin panel URL or button.	The system should block access and show an unauthorized message or redirect.	Access is denied and user is redirected or shown an error.	Successful
3	Observe system behavior.	Admin panel remains inaccessible to unauthorized users.	Admin panel is not accessible.	Successful

TABLE 5.43: Unit Test TC-14A – Access Admin Panel (Unauthorized User Attempt)

Test Case ID: TC-14C	Test Case Name: Approve Doctor Verification Request
Test Case Description: Verify that an admin can approve a pending doctor verification request and the user's status is updated accordingly.	Test Priority: High
Pre-Condition: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The user has submitted a valid doctor verification request. - The admin is logged in. 	Post-Condition: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The request is marked as approved. - The user's 'isVerifiedDoctor' flag is updated in the database.

Sr. No.	Action	Expected Result	Actual Result	Status
1	Log in as an admin and open the admin panel.	Admin dashboard should be displayed with pending requests section.	Admin panel is accessible.	Successful
2	Locate a pending doctor verification request.	The request details should be listed (e.g., name, documents).	Request is listed correctly.	Successful
3	Click “Approve” for the selected request.	The system should update the request status to “Approved.”	Request marked as approved.	Successful
4	Verify that the user’s Firestore record is updated.	The ‘isVerifiedDoctor’ flag should be set to true.	Database reflects verified status.	Successful

TABLE 5.44: Unit Test TC-14C – Approve Doctor Verification Request

5.2 Integration Testing

Integration testing ensures that different modules of the application work together seamlessly. It verifies data flow, communication between components, and functional consistency. Below is integrated tested features covering each feature of the application. We will proceed with detailed test cases one by one.

User Authentication and Authorization

This test will cover the following scenarios:

- User Signup: Ensures users can register using email and Google authentication.
- Email Confirmation: Verifies that a confirmation email is sent and required for account activation.
- User Login: Checks successful and failed login attempts with correct and incorrect credentials.
- Password Recovery: Ensures users can reset their password through the “Forgot Password” feature.
- Guest Login: Validates that users can access the app without an account using the “Continue as Guest” option.

-Session Management: Ensures user sessions persist correctly across logins and logouts.

Test Procedure Identifier	TP1
Purpose	To verify that user authentication methods (Signup, Login, Forgot Password, Google Sign-In, and Guest Login) function correctly and interact properly with the system.
Pre-Conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The system is connected to the internet. • Email confirmation system is active. • Google authentication service is enabled.
Procedure Steps	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sign up using an email and check if a confirmation email is received. • Attempt to log in before confirming the email. • Log in with correct credentials and check if access is granted. • Attempt to log in with incorrect credentials and verify error handling. • Use the "Forgot Password" feature and reset the password via email. • Sign up using "Continue with Google" and ensure account creation. • Access the app using the "Continue as Guest" feature.
Expected Results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Users should receive an email confirmation upon signup. • Unconfirmed accounts should not be able to log in. • Successful login should grant access, while incorrect attempts should display appropriate errors. • Password recovery emails should be sent, and users should be able to reset their passwords. • Google authentication should create and log in users seamlessly. • Guest login should allow limited access without an account.
Status	Successful

TABLE 5.45: Integration Test TP1 – User Authentication & Authorization

Community Management

This test will cover the following scenarios:

- Community Creation: Ensures that users can create a community and it appears in the list.
- Joining a Community: Checks if users can join public communities and receive necessary access rights.
- Leaving a Community: Verifies that leaving a community removes the user from the member list.
- Restricted Communities: Ensures private or restricted communities require approval before joining.
- Community Updates: Validates that community details and membership lists update properly.

Test Procedure Identifier	TP2
Purpose	To verify that users can create, join, and leave communities, and that these actions are correctly reflected in the system.
Pre-Conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The user is logged into the application. • The community management system is functional.
Procedure Steps	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create a new community and verify it appears in the community list. • Attempt to join a public community and confirm membership. • Leave a joined community and ensure removal from the member list. • Try to join a restricted community and verify the approval process. • Modify a community description and check if updates are saved.
Expected Results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Users should be able to create, join, and leave communities successfully. • Community lists should reflect the latest updates. • Restricted communities should require approval before joining. • Community details should be editable by authorized members.
Status	Successful

TABLE 5.46: Integration Test TP2 – Community Management

Post Creation and Interaction

This test will cover the following scenarios:

-Post Creation: Ensures that users can create posts and that they appear in the community feed.

-Upvoting and Downvoting: Verifies that votes update the post's ranking in real-time.

-Commenting: Checks if users can add, edit, and delete comments on posts. -Post Deletion: Ensures that users can remove their posts and that they disappear from the community feed.

-Real-Time Updates: Validates that interactions are reflected immediately across different user sessions.

Test Procedure Identifier	TP3
Purpose	To verify that users can create posts, interact with them through upvotes, downvotes, and comments, and that these interactions are accurately reflected in the system.
Pre-Conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The user is logged in and a member of a community. • The post creation and interaction system is functional.
Procedure Steps	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create a post and check if it appears in the community feed. • Upvote and downvote a post and verify if the vote count updates correctly. • Comment on a post and ensure the comment appears in the discussion thread. • Edit and delete a comment, verifying the changes reflect in real-time. • Delete a post and check if it disappears from the feed.
Expected Results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Posts should be created and displayed in the community feed. • Upvotes and downvotes should reflect immediately. • Comments should appear instantly, and edits/deletions should update the feed. • Deleted posts should be removed from the system.
Status	Successful

TABLE 5.47: Integration Test TP3 – Post Creation & Interaction

Search Functionality

This test will cover the following scenarios:

- Post Search: Ensures that users can search for posts using keywords and relevant filters.
- Community Search: Verifies that users can find communities by name or description.
- User Search: Checks if users can search for other members by username.
- Search Optimization: Ensures that the most relevant results appear first.
- Error Handling: Validates that invalid or empty searches return appropriate messages.

Test Procedure Identifier	TP4
Purpose	To verify that the search feature retrieves relevant posts, users, and communities based on user queries.
Pre-Conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The search feature is enabled. • The database contains posts, users, and communities.
Procedure Steps	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Search for a post using keywords and verify if relevant results appear. • Search for a community by name or description and check if the results are accurate. • Search for a user by entering a username and confirm that the correct user profile appears. • Conduct a search with random or non-existent terms and verify if an appropriate "No results found" message is displayed.
Expected Results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The search should return relevant results based on the input query. • Communities and users should be searchable by name. • Non-existent queries should return a "No results found" message. • Search results should be sorted based on relevance.
Status	Successful

TABLE 5.48: Integration Test TP4 – Search Functionality

Machine Learning Model Integration

This test will cover the following scenarios:

- Heart Disease Prediction: Ensures that users can input health-related data and receive predictions.
- Pneumonia Detection: Verifies that users can upload a chest X-ray and get a diagnosis.
- Error Handling: Checks how the system responds to invalid or corrupted files.
- Real-Time Response: Ensures that predictions are generated within an acceptable time frame.
- Result Interpretation: Validates that the model outputs are displayed correctly and clearly.

Test Procedure Identifier	TP5
Purpose	To validate the interaction between users and machine learning models for heart disease prediction and pneumonia detection.
Pre-Conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The user is logged in. • The ML models are deployed and accessible. • The system allows file uploads for pneumonia detection.
Procedure Steps	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Upload heart-related medical data and run a prediction. • Upload a chest X-ray image for pneumonia detection. • Verify if the model generates predictions successfully. • Attempt to upload an invalid or corrupt file and check the system's response. • Ensure the results are displayed correctly with necessary details.
Expected Results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Predictions should be generated based on the uploaded data. • Invalid inputs should trigger appropriate error messages. • Results should be displayed clearly and accurately. • Response times should be within an acceptable range.
Status	Successful

TABLE 5.49: Integration Test TP5 – Machine Learning Model Integration

Notifications System

This test will cover the following scenarios: -Post Interaction Notifications: Ensures that users receive notifications when their posts are upvoted, downvoted, or commented on.

-Community Notifications: Verifies that users are notified about updates in the communities they have joined.

-Real-Time Notifications: Ensures that notifications appear instantly when an action is performed.

-Notification Center Persistence: Checks that users can view past notifications in their notification center.

-Unread Notification Indicator: Validates that unread notifications are visually distinguishable.

Test Procedure Identifier	TP6
Purpose	To verify that users receive notifications for post interactions and community updates in real-time and that these notifications persist correctly.
Pre-Conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The user is logged in. • The notification system is enabled. • The user has existing posts or is part of a community.
Procedure Steps	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Upvote, downvote, or comment on a post and check if the post owner receives a notification. • Perform an activity in a community and verify if members receive relevant notifications. • Check if notifications appear instantly after an action. • View the notification center to verify if past notifications persist. • Ensure unread notifications have a visual indicator.
Expected Results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Notifications should be generated and displayed in real-time. • Users should receive relevant updates based on their activities. • Notifications should persist in the notification center for future reference. • Unread notifications should be clearly marked.
Status	Successful

TABLE 5.50: Integration Test TP6 – Notifications System

User Profile and Verification

This test will cover the following scenarios:

- Profile Updates: Ensures users can edit and save their personal details.
- Doctor Verification Request: Verifies that doctors can submit required credentials for verification.
- Document Upload: Checks if users can upload necessary verification documents.
- Profile Data Persistence: Ensures that saved profile changes remain after logging out and back in.
- Admin Review Process: Validates that verification requests are reflected in the admin dashboard.

Test Procedure Identifier	TP7
Purpose	To verify that users can update their profiles and submit doctor verification requests, and that these changes are properly stored and reviewed by the admin.
Pre-Conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The user is logged into the application. • The profile management system is functional. • The doctor verification process is enabled.
Procedure Steps	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Update profile details (e.g., name, bio, profile picture) and save changes. • Log out and log back in to ensure changes persist. • If the user is a doctor, fill out the verification form with required credentials. • Upload supporting documents (e.g., medical degree, registration certificate). • Submit the verification request and check if it appears in the admin dashboard.
Expected Results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Users should be able to update and save their profile details successfully. • Profile changes should persist after logging out and back in. • Doctor verification requests should be submitted and displayed for admin review. • Uploaded documents should be stored securely and be accessible for verification.
Status	Successful

TABLE 5.51: Integration Test TP7 – User Profile and Verification

Admin Dashboard

This test will cover the following scenarios: -View Verification Requests: Ensures that all pending doctor verification requests appear in the admin dashboard.

-Approval Process: Verifies that the admin can approve requests, granting verified status to doctors.

-Rejection Handling: Checks if admins can reject requests and notify users of the rejection.

-Status Updates: Ensures that the verification status is updated correctly in the user's profile.

-Security and Access Control: Validates that only admins have access to the dashboard and its functionalities.

Test Procedure Identifier	TP8
Purpose	To verify that the admin can manage doctor verification requests, including reviewing, approving, or rejecting them, and that the verification status updates correctly.
Pre-Conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The admin is logged into the system. • Users have submitted doctor verification requests. • The admin dashboard is functional.
Procedure Steps	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Navigate to the admin dashboard and view pending verification requests. • Open a verification request and review the submitted credentials. • Approve the request and verify that the user is marked as "Verified Doctor." • Reject a request and ensure that the user is notified of the rejection. • Attempt to access the admin dashboard with a non-admin account and confirm restricted access.
Expected Results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The admin should be able to view all pending verification requests. • Approved doctors should receive verified status in their profile. • Rejected requests should notify the user appropriately. • Non-admin users should not have access to the admin dashboard.
Status	Successful

TABLE 5.52: Integration Test TP8 – Admin Dashboard

Logout Functionality

This test will cover the following scenarios:

- Successful Logout: Ensures that clicking the logout button properly terminates the session.
- Session Expiry: Verifies that users are automatically logged out after a period of inactivity.
- Access Restriction Post-Logout: Checks that logged-out users cannot access authenticated features.
- Multiple Session Handling: Ensures that logging out from one device does not affect an active session on another device.
- Redirection Handling: Validates that users are correctly redirected to the login page after logging out.

Test Procedure Identifier	TP9
Purpose	To verify that the logout process successfully terminates user sessions, clears session data, and restricts access to authenticated features.
Pre-Conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The user is logged into the system. • The logout functionality is enabled.
Procedure Steps	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Click on the logout button and confirm that the user is logged out. • Attempt to access restricted features after logging out and check for redirection to the login page. • Remain inactive for an extended period and verify if the session expires automatically. • Log in on multiple devices and log out from one device, ensuring that other sessions remain unaffected. • After logging out, try using the "Back" button on the browser to check if session data is still accessible.
Expected Results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Users should be logged out and redirected to the login page. • Restricted features should be inaccessible post-logout. • Sessions should expire after a defined period of inactivity. • Logging out from one device should not impact other active sessions. • Browser navigation should not allow access to the previous session.
Status	Successful

TABLE 5.53: Integration Test TP9 – Logout Functionality

5.3 System Testing

System testing is a type of software testing that evaluates the complete and integrated system to ensure it meets the specified requirements. It is performed after unit and integration testing to verify the system's functionality, security, performance, and overall behavior. This testing helps identify defects, ensure all components work together correctly, and validate that the system meets business and user expectations before deployment. System testing is crucial to detect issues early, reduce risks, and enhance software quality.

Sign-up using "Continue with Google"

This test case verifies the functionality of signing up using the "Continue with Google" option. The goal is to ensure that users can authenticate with their Google accounts without encountering errors. It also checks whether the application correctly redirects authenticated users to the homepage and whether invalid or canceled authentication attempts are handled properly.

Test Case ID	ST-01	Test Case Description	Sign-up using “Continue with Google”
Created By	M. Umar	Reviewed By	Zain Ali
Version	1.0		

Prerequisites	
S. No.	Condition
1	Have an active internet connection
2	Google account should be logged in on the device
3	App should be installed on an Android phone
4	The ”Sign-up using Continue with Google” button should be visible on the sign-up screen

Environment	Android Phone
--------------------	---------------

Test Data	
1	Email: umar.mualij@gmail.com
2	Password: 786492

Step	Step Detail	Expected Results	Actual Results	Pass/Fail
1	Open the app	App must open, and the splash screen should be displayed	As Expected	Pass
2	Navigate to the Sign-up screen	The sign-up screen should be displayed	As Expected	Pass
3	Click on ”Continue with Google”	A Google account selection prompt should appear	As Expected	Pass
4	Select a valid Google account	The account should be selected, and authentication should begin	As Expected	Pass
5	Complete the authentication process	The user should be successfully signed up and redirected to the homepage	As Expected	Pass

TABLE 5.54: System Test ST-01 – Sign-up using “Continue with Google”

Sign-up using Email

Test Case ID	ST-02	Test Case Description	Sign-up using Email
Created By	M. Umar	Reviewed By	Zain Ali
Version	1.0		

Prerequisites	
S. No.	Condition
1	Have an active internet connection
2	App should be installed on an Android phone
3	The "Sign-up with Email" button should be visible on the sign-up screen

Environment	Android Phone
--------------------	---------------

Test Data	
1	Email: umar.mualij@gmail.com
2	Password: 786492

Step	Step Detail	Expected Results	Actual Results	Pass/Fail
1	Open the app	App must open, and the splash screen should be displayed	As Expected	Pass
2	Navigate to the Sign-up screen	The sign-up screen should be displayed	As Expected	Pass
3	Enter a valid email and password	Credentials should be accepted	As Expected	Pass
4	Click the "Sign-up" button	A confirmation message should be sent to the registered email	As Expected	Pass
5	Verify the email by clicking the confirmation link	The user should be verified and redirected to the home-page	As Expected	Pass

TABLE 5.55: System Test ST-02 – Sign-up using Email

Sign-up Confirmation Email

Test Case ID	ST-03	Test Case Description	Sign-up Confirmation Email
Created By	M. Umar	Reviewed By	Zain Ali
Version	1.0		

Prerequisites	
S. No.	Condition
1	Have an active internet connection
2	App should be installed on an Android phone
3	A valid email must be used for registration
4	The sign-up process must be completed

Environment	Android Phone
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Test Data	
1	Email: umar.mualij@gmail.com
2	Password: 786492

Step	Step Detail	Expected Results	Actual Results	Pass/Fail
1	Sign up using a valid email and password	A confirmation email should be sent to the registered email address	As Expected	Pass
2	Open the email inbox	The confirmation email should be visible	As Expected	Pass
3	Click the verification link in the email	The user should be redirected to the verification page	As Expected	Pass
4	Complete the verification process	The user should be successfully verified and redirected to the homepage	As Expected	Pass
5	Attempt to use an expired or invalid verification link	The system should display an error message	As Expected	Pass

TABLE 5.56: System Test ST-03 – Sign-up Confirmation Email

Login using Email and Password

Test Case ID	ST-04	Test Case Description	Login using Email and Password
Created By	M. Umar	Reviewed By	Zain Ali
Version	1.0		

Prerequisites	
S. No.	Condition
1	Have an active internet connection
2	App should be installed on an Android phone
3	User must have a registered email and password
4	The login screen should be accessible

Environment	Android Phone
--------------------	---------------

Test Data	
1	Email: umar.muallij@gmail.com
2	Password: 786492

Step	Step Detail	Expected Results	Actual Results	Pass/Fail
1	Open the app	App must open, and the splash screen should be displayed	As Expected	Pass
2	Navigate to the Login screen	The login screen should be displayed	As Expected	Pass
3	Enter a valid email and password	Credentials should be accepted	As Expected	Pass
4	Click the "Login" button	The user should be redirected to the homepage	As Expected	Pass
5	Enter an incorrect password and attempt login	The system should display an "Incorrect Password" error	As Expected	Pass
6	Enter an unregistered email and attempt login	The system should display a "User Not Found" error	As Expected	Pass
7	Leave the email and password fields empty and attempt login	The system should prompt the user to enter credentials	As Expected	Pass

TABLE 5.57: System Test ST-04 – Login using Email and Password

Recover Password using "Forgot Password"

Test Case ID	ST-05	Test Case Description	Recover Password using "Forgot Password"
Created By	M. Umar	Reviewed By	Zain Ali
Version	1.0		

Prerequisites	
S. No.	Condition
1	Have an active internet connection
2	App should be installed on an Android phone
3	User must have a registered email
4	The "Forgot Password" option should be visible on the login screen

Environment	Android Phone
--------------------	---------------

Test Data	
1	Email: umar.mualij@gmail.com

Step	Step Detail	Expected Results	Actual Results	Pass/Fail
1	Open the app	App must open, and the splash screen should be displayed	As Expected	Pass
2	Navigate to the Login screen	The login screen should be displayed	As Expected	Pass
3	Click on "Forgot Password"	The password recovery page should be displayed	As Expected	Pass
4	Enter a registered email and submit	A password reset email should be sent	As Expected	Pass
5	Open the email and click the reset link	The user should be redirected to the reset password page	As Expected	Pass
6	Enter a new password and confirm	The password should be updated successfully	As Expected	Pass
7	Attempt to use an expired or invalid reset link	The system should display an error message	As Expected	Pass
8	Enter an unregistered email and submit	The system should display "User Not Found" error	As Expected	Pass

TABLE 5.58: System Test ST-05 – Recover Password using "Forgot Password"

Continue as a Guest

Test Case ID	ST-06	Test Case Description	Continue as a Guest
Created By	M. Umar	Reviewed By	Zain Ali
Version	1.0		

Prerequisites	
S. No.	Condition
1	Have an active internet connection
2	App should be installed on an Android phone
3	The "Continue as Guest" option should be visible on the login screen

Environment	Android Phone
--------------------	---------------

Test Data	
1	No credentials required

Step	Step Detail	Expected Results	Actual Results	Pass/Fail
1	Open the app	App must open, and the splash screen should be displayed	As Expected	Pass
2	Navigate to the Login screen	The login screen should be displayed	As Expected	Pass
3	Click on "Continue as Guest"	The user should be redirected to the app's homepage with limited access	As Expected	Pass
4	Attempt to access a feature requiring authentication	The system should prompt the user to log in or sign up	As Expected	Pass
5	Navigate through available guest-accessible sections	The user should be able to explore without restrictions	As Expected	Pass
6	Attempt to create an account from guest mode	The user should be able to sign up and transition to a registered account	As Expected	Pass

TABLE 5.59: System Test ST-06 – Continue as a Guest

Test Case ID	ST-07	Test Case Description	Create a Community
Created By	M. Umar	Reviewed By	Zain Ali
Version	1.0		

Prerequisites	
S. No.	Condition
1	Have an active internet connection
2	App should be installed on an Android phone
3	User must be logged in
4	The "Create Community" option should be visible in the app

Environment	Android Phone
--------------------	---------------

Test Data	
1	Email: umar.mualij@gmail.com
2	Password: 786492
3	Community Name: Cardiologists
4	Community Description: A space for Heart specialists

Step	Step Detail	Expected Results	Actual Results	Pass/Fail
1	Open the app	App must open, and the splash screen should be displayed	As Expected	Pass
2	Log in with valid credentials	The user should be successfully logged in	As Expected	Pass
3	Navigate to the "Create Community" option	The community creation page should be displayed	As Expected	Pass
4	Enter a unique community name and description, then submit	The community should be created successfully	As Expected	Pass
5	Attempt to create a community with an existing name	The system should display a "Community name already taken" error	As Expected	Pass
6	Try to create a community without entering a name	The system should prompt the user to enter a name	As Expected	Pass
7	Verify that the newly created community appears in the community list	The community should be visible in the list	As Expected	Pass

TABLE 5.60: System Test ST-07 – Create a Community

Join a Community

Test Case ID	ST-08	Test Case Description	Join a Community
Created By	M. Umar	Reviewed By	Zain Ali
Version	1.0		

Prerequisites	
S. No.	Condition
1	Have an active internet connection
2	App should be installed on an Android phone
3	User must be logged in
4	At least one community must exist in the app
5	The "Join" button should be visible for communities

Environment	Android Phone
--------------------	---------------

Test Data	
1	Email: umar.mualij@gmail.com
2	Password: 786492
3	Community Name: Cardiologists

Step	Step Detail	Expected Results	Actual Results	Pass/Fail
1	Open the app	App must open, and the splash screen should be displayed	As Expected	Pass
2	Log in with valid credentials	The user should be successfully logged in	As Expected	Pass
3	Navigate to the "Search" section	The list of available communities should be displayed	As Expected	Pass
4	Click on the "Join" button for a selected community	The user should be added as a member of the community	As Expected	Pass
5	Try to join a community the user is already a member of	The system should display a message stating "You are already a member"	As Expected	Pass
6	Verify that the joined community appears in the user's community list	The community should be visible under "My Communities"	As Expected	Pass

TABLE 5.61: System Test ST-08 – Join a Community

Test Case ID	ST-09	Test Case Description	Add a Post in a Community
Created By	M. Umar	Reviewed By	Zain Ali
Version	1.0		

Prerequisites	
S. No.	Condition
1	Have an active internet connection
2	App should be installed on an Android phone
3	User must be logged in
4	User must be a member of at least one community
5	The "Create Post" option should be visible within the community

Environment	Android Phone
--------------------	---------------

Test Data	
1	Email: umar.mualij@gmail.com
2	Password: 786492
3	Post Content: "Latest advancements in Medical fields are fascinating!"

Step	Step Detail	Expected Results	Actual Results	Pass/Fail
1	Open the app	App must open, and the splash screen should be displayed	As Expected	Pass
2	Log in with valid credentials	The user should be successfully logged in	As Expected	Pass
3	Navigate to the "Communities" section and select a community	The selected community should open	As Expected	Pass
4	Click on "Create Post"	The post creation screen should appear	As Expected	Pass
5	Enter valid post content and submit	The post should be successfully created and visible in the community	As Expected	Pass
6	Attempt to submit an empty post	The system should display a validation message "Post content cannot be empty"	As Expected	Pass
7	Enter a post exceeding the character limit and submit	The system should display an error "Post exceeds character limit"	As Expected	Pass
8	Verify that the new post appears in the community feed	The post should be displayed under the community's post section	As Expected	Pass

TABLE 5.62: System Test ST-09 – Add a Post in a Community

Test Case ID	ST-10	Test Case Description	Interact with a Post (Upvote, Downvote, and Comment)
Created By	M. Umar	Reviewed By	Zain Ali
Version	1.0		

Prerequisites	
S. No.	Condition
1	Have an active internet connection
2	App should be installed on an Android phone
3	User must be logged in
4	User must be a member of at least one community
5	At least one post must exist in the selected community
6	The "Upvote," "Downvote," and "Comment" options should be visible for posts

Environment	Android Phone
--------------------	---------------

Test Data	
1	Email: umar.mualij@gmail.com
2	Password: 786492
3	Comment: "Great insights! Thanks for sharing."

Step	Step Detail	Expected Results	Actual Results	Pass/Fail
1	Open the app	App must open, and the splash screen should be displayed	As Expected	Pass
2	Log in with valid credentials	The user should be successfully logged in	As Expected	Pass
3	Navigate to the "Communities" section and select a community	The selected community should open	As Expected	Pass
4	Locate a post and click the "Upvote" button	The post's upvote count should increase by one	As Expected	Pass
5	Click the "Downvote" button after upvoting	The upvote should be removed, and the downvote count should increase by one	As Expected	Pass
6	Enter a valid comment and submit	The comment should be posted and visible under the post	As Expected	Pass
7	Attempt to upvote or downvote the same post multiple times	The system should not allow multiple votes from the same user	As Expected	Pass

TABLE 5.63: System Test ST-10 – Interact with a Post (Upvote, Downvote, and Comment)

Test Case ID	ST-11	Test Case Description	Search for a Post, User, or Community
Created By	M. Umar	Reviewed By	Zain Ali
Version	1.0		

Prerequisites	
S. No.	Condition
1	Have an active internet connection
2	App should be installed on an Android phone
3	User must be logged in
4	The "Search" option should be available in the app
5	At least one post, user, and community should exist in the system

Environment	Android Phone
--------------------	---------------

Test Data	
1	Email: umar.mualij@gmail.com
2	Password: 786492
3	Search Keyword: "Machine Learning" (For posts)
4	Search Keyword: "Dr. Ahmed" (For users)
5	Search Keyword: "AI Community" (For communities)
6	Search Keyword: "xyz123" (Invalid search)

Step	Step Detail	Expected Results	Actual Results	Pass/Fail
1	Open the app	App must open, and the splash screen should be displayed	As Expected	Pass
2	Log in with valid credentials	The user should be successfully logged in	As Expected	Pass
3	Click on the "Search" icon	The search bar should appear	As Expected	Pass
4	Enter a keyword related to an existing post and search	Relevant posts should be displayed in the results	As Expected	Pass
5	Enter a keyword related to an existing user and search	The corresponding user should appear in the search results	As Expected	Pass
6	Enter a keyword related to an existing community and search	The relevant community should be displayed in the results	As Expected	Pass
7	Enter a random or invalid keyword and search	The system should display "No results found"	As Expected	Pass
8	Attempt to search without entering any keyword	The system should display "Please enter a search term"	As Expected	Pass

TABLE 5.64: System Test ST-11 – Search for a Post, User, or Community

Test Case ID	ST-12	Test Case Description	Interact with Machine Learning Models
Created By	M. Umar	Reviewed By	Zain Ali
Version	1.0		

Prerequisites	
S. No.	Condition
1	Have an active internet connection
2	App should be installed on an Android phone
3	User must be logged in
4	The "Heart Disease Prediction" and "Pneumonia Detection" features should be available

Environment	Android Phone
--------------------	---------------

Test Data	
1	Email: umar.mualij@gmail.com
2	Password: 786492
3	Heart Prediction Input: Age: 45, Cholesterol Level: 220, Blood Pressure: 140/90
4	Pneumonia Prediction Input: Valid Chest X-ray Image
5	Invalid Heart Prediction Input: Age: "", Cholesterol Level: "", Blood Pressure: ""
6	Invalid Pneumonia Prediction Input: Non-X-ray Image

Step	Step Detail	Expected Results	Actual Results	Pass/Fail
1	Open the app	App must open, and the splash screen should be displayed	As Expected	Pass
2	Log in with valid credentials	The user should be successfully logged in	As Expected	Pass
3	Navigate to the "Machine Learning Models" section	The section should display both heart disease and pneumonia prediction models	As Expected	Pass
4	Click on "Heart Disease Prediction" and enter valid inputs	The system should process the data and provide a risk assessment	As Expected	Pass
5	Click on "Pneumonia Detection" and upload a valid chest X-ray	The system should analyze the image and return a diagnosis	As Expected	Pass
6	Enter invalid inputs for heart prediction (empty fields)	The system should display an error message prompting for valid data	As Expected	Pass
7	Upload a non-X-ray image for pneumonia detection	The system should reject the image and display an error	As Expected	Pass

TABLE 5.65: System Test ST-12 – Interact with Machine Learning Models

Test Case ID	ST-13	Test Case Description	Receive Notifications for Posts and Community Activities
Created By	M. Umar	Reviewed By	Zain Ali
Version	1.0		

Prerequisites	
S. No.	Condition
1	Have an active internet connection
2	App should be installed on an Android phone
3	User must be logged in
4	User must have at least one post or be part of a community
5	Notifications must be enabled in device and app settings

Environment	Android Phone
--------------------	---------------

Test Data	
1	Email: umar.mualij@gmail.com
2	Password: 786492
3	A test post created by the user
4	User is a member of “Cardiologist”
5	Another user comments on the test post
6	Another user upvotes the test post
7	A new post is added in “Cardiologist”
8	A system-generated notification (e.g., update reminder)

Step	Step Detail	Expected Results	Actual Results	Pass/Fail
1	Open the app	App must open, and the splash screen should be displayed	As Expected	Pass
2	Log in with valid credentials	The user should be successfully logged in	As Expected	Pass
3	Navigate to the “Notifications” section	The section should be accessible	As Expected	Pass
4	Another user comments on the test post	A notification should appear for the comment	As Expected	Pass
5	Another user upvotes the test post	A notification should appear for the upvote	As Expected	Pass
6	A new post is added in “AI Community”	A notification should be sent to the user	As Expected	Pass
7	A system-generated notification is triggered	The system should send the appropriate notification	As Expected	Pass
8	Click on a notification	The app should navigate to the relevant post or section	As Expected	Pass

TABLE 5.66: Screenshot of Test Case ST-13: Receive Notifications for Posts and Community

Manage User Profile

Test Case ID	ST-14	Test Case Description	Manage User Profile
Created By	M. Umar	Reviewed By	Zain Ali
Version	1.0		

Prerequisites	
S. No.	Condition
1	Have an active internet connection
2	App should be installed on an Android phone
3	User must be logged in
4	The "Profile" section should be accessible

Environment	Android Phone
--------------------	---------------

Test Data	
1	Email: umar.mualij@gmail.com
2	Password: 786492
3	New Name: Umar M.
4	New Profile Picture: Valid image file
5	Invalid Profile Picture: Corrupt or unsupported file

Step	Step Detail	Expected Results	Actual Results	Pass/Fail
1	Open the app	App must open, and the splash screen should be displayed	As Expected	Pass
2	Log in with valid credentials	The user should be successfully logged in	As Expected	Pass
3	Navigate to the "Profile" section	The profile section should be displayed	As Expected	Pass
4	Edit the profile name and save changes	The new name should be updated and displayed	As Expected	Pass
5	Upload a valid profile picture	The picture should be successfully updated	As Expected	Pass
6	Upload an invalid profile picture	The system should reject the file and display an error	As Expected	Pass
7	Log out and log back in	The updated profile information should persist	As Expected	Pass

TABLE 5.67: System Test ST-14 – Manage User Profile

Doctor Verification Process

Test Case ID	ST-15	Test Case Description	Doctor Verification Process
Created By	M. Umar	Reviewed By	Zain Ali
Version	1.0		

Prerequisites	
1	App installed, connected to internet, user logged in
2	Doctor Verification section accessible
3	Admin can access pending requests

Environment	Android Phone
--------------------	---------------

Test Data	
1	Email: umar.mualij@gmail.com
2	Password: 786492
3	Registration No.: D-123456
4	Full Name: Dr. Umar M.
5	Father's Name: Waris
6	Reg Type: General Practitioner
7	Status: Active
8	Issue: 01/01/2020, Expiry: 01/01/2025
9	Valid Degree (PDF), Invalid File

Step	Step Detail	Expected Result	Actual Result	Status
1	Open the app	App and splash screen appear	As Expected	Pass
2	Log in	User is logged in	As Expected	Pass
3	Navigate to verification section	Form is visible	As Expected	Pass
4	Enter credentials	Request sent for review	As Expected	Pass
5	Upload valid file	File uploaded successfully	As Expected	Pass
6	Upload invalid file	Error shown for file type	As Expected	Pass
7	Admin logs in	Pending request visible	As Expected	Pass
8	Admin approves request	User gets verification notice	As Expected	Pass
9	Admin rejects request	User sees rejection with reason	As Expected	Pass
10	Verified user logs in again	"Verified Doctor" label shown	As Expected	Pass

TABLE 5.68: System Test ST-15 – Doctor Verification Process

Admin Dashboard for Doctor Verification

Test Case ID	ST-16	Test Case Description	Admin Dashboard for Doctor Verification
Created By	M. Umar	Reviewed By	Zain Ali
Version	1.0		

Prerequisites	
1	Internet, app installed, admin logged in
2	At least one pending doctor request
3	Admin dashboard accessible

Environment	Android Phone
--------------------	---------------

Test Data	
1	Admin Email: admin@example.com
2	Password: admin123
3	Request: Dr. Umar M. – D-123456
4	Verification Status: Pending
5	Options: Approve / Reject

Step	Step Detail	Expected Result	Actual Result	Status
1	Open app	Splash screen is displayed	As Expected	Pass
2	Log in as admin	Admin successfully logged in	As Expected	Pass
3	Open Admin Dashboard	Dashboard section loads	As Expected	Pass
4	View pending requests	All requests listed	As Expected	Pass
5	Select request	Doctor details appear	As Expected	Pass
6	Review credentials	Submitted info is viewable	As Expected	Pass
7	Approve request	Status becomes “Verified”	As Expected	Pass
8	Reject with reason	Rejection message sent	As Expected	Pass
9	Search doctor	Verified label appears	As Expected	Pass

TABLE 5.69: System Test ST-16 – Admin Dashboard for Doctor Verification

Logout Functionality

Test Case ID	ST-17	Test Case Description	Logout Functionality
Created By	M. Umar	Reviewed By	Zain Ali
Version	1.0		

Prerequisites	
S. No.	Condition
1	Have an active internet connection
2	App should be installed on an Android phone
3	User must be logged in
4	Logout button should be visible in the app

Environment	Android Phone
--------------------	---------------

Test Data	
1	Email: umar.mualij@gmail.com
2	Password: 786492

Step	Step Detail	Expected Results	Actual Results	Pass/Fail
1	Open the app	App must open, and the splash screen should be displayed	As Expected	Pass
2	Log in with valid credentials	The user should be successfully logged in	As Expected	Pass
3	Navigate to the logout option	The logout button should be visible	As Expected	Pass
4	Click the logout button	The user should be logged out and redirected to the login screen	As Expected	Pass
5	Try to access a restricted area without logging in	The app should prompt for login	As Expected	Pass
6	Log in again with valid credentials	The user should be successfully logged in	As Expected	Pass

TABLE 5.70: System Test ST-17 – Logout Functionality

5.4 Performance Testing

Performance testing is a non-functional testing technique used to determine how an application will behave under various conditions. The goal is to test its responsiveness, scalability, and stability in real-world scenarios. Performance testing ensures that an application can handle expected and peak loads effectively without degradation in performance.

Performance testing is divided into different categories, including:

- Load Testing: Checks how the system performs under expected load.
- Stress Testing: Determines the system's stability by pushing it beyond its normal operational capacity.
- Spike Testing: Evaluates performance when the system faces sudden surges in traffic.
- Scalability Testing: Assesses the application's ability to scale up or down based on demand.

Load Testing

Load testing evaluates the system's ability to handle expected user loads without performance degradation. It helps identify bottlenecks and ensures the application remains responsive under normal conditions.

Sr. No	Functionality	Estimated Load Time (seconds)
1	Signup using Continue with Google	1.0 to 2.5
2	Signup through Email	1.5 to 3.0
3	Confirmation email sent	2.0 to 3.5
4	Login using Email and Password	0.5 to 1.2
5	Recover Password (Forgot Password)	1.0 to 2.5
6	Continue as a Guest	0.5 to 1.2
7	Create a Community	1.0 to 2.5
8	Join a Community	0.8 to 1.5
9	Add a Post in a Community	1.2 to 2.5
10	Interact with a Post (Upvote, Downvote, Comment)	0.5 to 1.2
11	Search Bar (Search Post, User, or Community)	1.0 to 2.0
12	Interact with Heart Prediction Model	2.5 to 4.0
13	Interact with Pneumonia Prediction Model	3.0 to 4.5
14	Get Notifications	0.5 to 1.5
15	Manage Profile	1.0 to 2.5
16	Get Verified as a Doctor	2.5 to 4.0
17	Admin Dashboard for Doctor Verification	3.0 to 5.0
18	Logout	0.5 to 1.0

TABLE 5.71: Load Testing

Stress Testing

Stress testing pushes the system beyond its normal operational capacity to determine its breaking point. It helps identify the system's limits and failure points when handling extreme conditions, such as high concurrent users or data loads.

Sr. No	Functionality	Estimated Load Time (seconds)
1	Signup using Continue with Google	1.5 to 3.0
2	Signup through Email	2.0 to 4.0
3	Confirmation email sent	3.0 to 5.0
4	Login using Email and Password	1.0 to 2.5
5	Recover Password (Forgot Password)	2.0 to 4.0
6	Continue as a Guest	1.0 to 2.5
7	Create a Community	1.5 to 3.0
8	Join a Community	1.0 to 2.5
9	Add a Post in a Community	2.0 to 4.0
10	Interact with a Post (Upvote, Downvote, Comment)	1.0 to 2.5
11	Search Bar (Search Post, User, or Community)	1.5 to 3.0
12	Interact with Heart Prediction Model	3.0 to 5.5
13	Interact with Pneumonia Prediction Model	4.0 to 6.0
14	Get Notifications	1.0 to 2.0
15	Manage Profile	1.5 to 3.0
16	Get Verified as a Doctor	3.0 to 5.5
17	Admin Dashboard for Doctor Verification	4.0 to 6.5
18	Logout	1.0 to 2.0

TABLE 5.72: Stress Testing – Estimated Load Time for Functionalities

Spike Testing

Spike testing examines how the system handles sudden surges in traffic. It ensures that the application does not crash or become unresponsive when a large number of users access it simultaneously.

Sr. No	Functionality	Estimated Load Time (seconds)
1	Signup using Continue with Google	2.0 to 4.0
2	Login using Email and Password	1.5 to 3.5
3	Add a Post in a Community	2.5 to 5.0
4	Interact with a Post	1.5 to 3.5
5	Search Bar	2.0 to 4.5
6	Interact with Heart Prediction Model	4.0 to 6.5
7	Interact with Pneumonia Prediction Model	5.0 to 7.5
8	Get Notifications	1.5 to 3.5

TABLE 5.73: Spike Testing – Estimated Load Time for Functionalities

Scalability Testing

Scalability testing evaluates the system's ability to handle increased workloads by scaling resources dynamically. It ensures that performance remains consistent as user load grows.

Sr. No	Functionality	Scaling Behavior
1	Signup Process	Scales efficiently with cloud resources
2	Login System	Manages increasing users with auto-scaling
3	Community Creation	Handles high traffic with load balancing
4	Machine Learning Predictions	Scales horizontally with additional GPU instances
5	Notification System	Adapts to increasing user notifications
6	Admin Dashboard	Scales vertically for heavy data processing

TABLE 5.74: Scalability Testing – System Behavior under Increased Load

5.5 Security Testing

Security testing is a crucial process that ensures an application is protected against vulnerabilities, threats, and unauthorized access. It evaluates the system's ability to safeguard user data, prevent malicious attacks, and maintain confidentiality, integrity, and availability. In Firebase-based applications, security testing is essential to validate Firestore security rules, authentication mechanisms, and data protection strategies. This process helps identify potential weaknesses before they can be exploited, ensuring a secure and reliable user experience.

Integrity

Integrity ensures that the application's data stored in Firebase remains unaltered unless modified by an authorized user. It prevents unauthorized changes, ensures data consistency, and validates Firebase security rules to protect against manipulation. These test cases verify that user profiles, posts, notifications, and sensitive information remain intact and uncorrupted.

Test ID	Test Case	Description	Expected Result	Actual Result
INT-01	User Profile Data Integrity	Ensure user profile data remains unchanged unless updated by the user.	Profile updates should persist and remain unchanged unless edited.	As Expected
INT-02	Post and Comment Integrity	Ensure posts/comments remain unchanged unless modified by the owner.	Only the post owner can edit/delete their content.	As Expected
INT-03	Secure File Upload in Firebase Storage	Validate uploaded files (e.g., degrees) remain unaltered.	Files should be securely stored and not modifiable.	As Expected
INT-04	Password Reset Token Integrity	Ensure reset tokens expire and can't be reused.	Expired or used tokens must be invalid.	As Expected
INT-05	Notification Data Consistency	Verify notifications are accurate and persist.	Notifications should remain unchanged unless deleted.	As Expected
INT-06	Firestore Rules Enforcement	Ensure unauthorized requests can't modify Firestore data.	Unauthorized changes should be rejected.	As Expected

TABLE 5.75: Security Test ST-01 – Integrity Security Test Cases

Confidentiality

Confidentiality ensures that sensitive user data is only accessible to authorized users. It prevents unauthorized access, data leaks, and exposure of personal information. In a Firebase-based application, confidentiality is enforced through Firestore security rules, Firebase Authentication, and encrypted data storage. These test cases validate that user credentials, private messages, and verification documents are securely stored and accessed only by permitted users.

ID	Test Case	Description	Expected Result	Actual Result	Result
CONF-01	Secure Auth Data	Ensure credentials are never exposed in plain text.	Credentials encrypted.	As Expected	Pass
CONF-02	Private Data Protection	Personal info (email, phone) must remain private.	Visible only to owner.	As Expected	Pass
CONF-03	Verification Docs Privacy	Uploaded docs only visible to admin.	Docs hidden from users.	As Expected	Pass
CONF-04	Private Messaging Rules	Messages should not be accessible to others.	Only sender/receiver access.	As Expected	Pass
CONF-05	API Access Restriction	API requiring token should block unauthorized access.	Invalid requests denied.	As Expected	Pass
CONF-06	Secure Transmission	Data should travel over HTTPS only.	Encrypted in transit.	As Expected	Pass

TABLE 5.76: Security Test ST-02 – Confidentiality Security Test Cases

Authentication

Authentication ensures that only legitimate users can access the application by verifying their identity through Firebase Authentication. It prevents unauthorized access by enforcing secure login mechanisms such as email-password authentication, Google sign-in, and password recovery. These test cases validate that user authentication is secure, properly implemented, and resistant to common attacks like brute force and session hijacking.

ID	Test Case	Description	Expected Result	Actual Result	Result
AUTH-01	Email & Password Login	Users log in with email/-password.	Valid logins allowed; invalid denied.	As Expected	Pass
AUTH-02	Google Sign-In	Users sign in via Google.	Google login must work securely.	As Expected	Pass
AUTH-03	Password Recovery	Forgot Password sends email and allows reset.	Reset email sent, password updated.	As Expected	Pass
AUTH-04	Multi-Session Handling	Prevent concurrent logins if restricted.	Only valid sessions remain.	As Expected	Pass
AUTH-05	Brute Force Defense	Detect repeated login failures.	Security checks triggered.	As Expected	Pass
AUTH-06	Session Expiry	Logout user after inactivity or expiration.	Auto logout works.	As Expected	Pass

TABLE 5.77: Security Test ST-03 – Authentication Security Test Cases

Authorization

Authorization ensures that users can only access the features and data they are permitted to based on their roles and permissions. It prevents unauthorized users from performing restricted actions, such as modifying admin settings or accessing confidential information. In Firebase, this is enforced through Firestore security rules and role-based access control (RBAC). These test cases validate that the system correctly differentiates between users, doctors, and admins, restricting their access accordingly.

ID	Test Case	Description	Expected Result	Actual Result	Result
AUTHZ-01	Role-Based Access Control (RBAC)	Validate role-based access for users and admins.	Users restricted; admins have full access.	As Expected	Pass
AUTHZ-02	Community Post Moderation	Only community admins can pin/delete posts.	Only authorized admins allowed.	As Expected	Pass
AUTHZ-03	Doctor Verification Approval	Only admin can manage doctor requests.	Users blocked from access.	As Expected	Pass
AUTHZ-04	Restricted Admin Access	Non-admins shouldn't access the admin panel.	Only admins can view/-manage dashboard.	As Expected	Pass
AUTHZ-05	Firestore Security Enforcement	Prevent unauthorized Firestore modifications.	Unauthorized writes denied.	As Expected	Pass
AUTHZ-06	Unauthorized API Access	API with admin privilege should be protected.	Requests blocked by rules.	As Expected	Pass

TABLE 5.78: Security Test ST-04 – Authorization Security Test Cases

Availability

Availability ensures that the application remains accessible and operational under various conditions, including high traffic, unexpected failures, and denial-of-service (DoS) attacks. In a Firebase-based application, availability is maintained through efficient database queries, rate limiting, and error handling mechanisms. These test cases validate that the system remains functional, responsive, and resistant to disruptions.

ID	Test Case	Description	Expected Result	Actual Result	Result
AVAIL-01	System Uptime Monitoring	Verify system remains responsive under normal load.	No downtime; system functions normally.	As Expected	Pass
AVAIL-02	High Traffic Handling	Ensure the system supports multiple concurrent users.	Remains stable during high traffic.	As Expected	Pass
AVAIL-03	Firebase Rate Limiting	Block excessive API requests to prevent abuse.	Excess requests rejected with error.	As Expected	Pass
AVAIL-04	Recovery from Failures	System should recover from minor issues without help.	Auto restart or reroute.	As Expected	Pass
AVAIL-05	DoS Attack Prevention	Detect/block abuse from repeated requests.	Abusive IP blocked.	As Expected	Pass
AVAIL-06	Offline Mode Support	Limited access and sync after reconnect.	Cached data available, sync on return.	As Expected	Pass

TABLE 5.79: Security Test ST-05 – Availability Security Test Cases

Non-Repudiation

Non-repudiation ensures that users cannot deny actions they have performed within the application. This is achieved through logging, audit trails, and confirmation mechanisms. In a Firebase-based system, authentication logs, timestamps, and verification emails help maintain accountability. These test cases validate that all critical actions are logged and properly attributed to the responsible users.

ID	Test Case	Description	Expected Result	Actual Result	Result
NR-01	Login & Logout Audit Logs	Ensure login/logout events are logged with timestamps.	Auth events recorded with time.	As Expected	Pass
NR-02	Action Logging for Posts	Record post create/delete/update with user info.	Actions recorded and retrievable.	As Expected	Pass
NR-03	Doctor Verification Logs	Log verification requests and decisions.	Logs include timestamps.	As Expected	Pass
NR-04	Email Confirmations	Log and notify on email/pass changes.	Email confirmation sent.	As Expected	Pass
NR-05	Firestore Activity Logs	Track database changes with identity and time.	Changes tracked with user ID.	As Expected	Pass
NR-06	Notification of Account Activity	Notify users of sensitive account events.	Notification sent to user.	As Expected	Pass

TABLE 5.80: Security Test ST-06 – Non-Repudiation Security Test Cases

5.6 Usability Testing

Usability testing is a non-functional testing technique used to evaluate how user-friendly an application is. It assesses how easily users can interact with the system, navigate different features, and complete tasks efficiently. The primary goal is to identify issues that might hinder the user experience, such as complex navigation, unclear instructions, or inefficient workflows.

We conduct usability testing to:

- Ensure the application is intuitive and easy to use.
- Identify any obstacles that may slow down or frustrate users.
- Improve user satisfaction and engagement.
- Reduce errors by making processes clearer and more efficient.

S. No.	Test Data
1	After logging into the application, the homepage displays all features clearly.
2	User can sign up using “Continue with Google” without confusion.
3	User can sign up via email, and the confirmation message is received successfully.
4	User can log in using email and password without any usability issues.
5	The “Forgot Password” feature allows users to recover their accounts smoothly.
6	Users can continue as a guest and browse without issues.
7	Users can create a community, add details, and publish successfully.
8	Users can join a community and interact with posts easily.
9	Users can add posts in a community without facing UI difficulties.
10	Users can upvote, downvote, and comment on posts without confusion.
11	The search bar allows users to find posts, users, or communities efficiently.
12	Users can interact with the heart disease prediction model easily.
13	Users can interact with the pneumonia prediction model without usability challenges.
14	Notifications are received and displayed correctly.
15	Users can access and manage their profiles without difficulty.
16	The doctor verification form is clear, and users can input credentials smoothly.
17	The admin dashboard for doctor verification is user-friendly.
18	Users can log out without confusion or errors.

TABLE 5.81: Usability Testing Table

5.7 Compatibility Testing

Compatibility testing ensures that an application works seamlessly across various devices, operating systems, browsers, and screen resolutions. It helps verify that the application’s UI, functionalities, and performance remain consistent regardless of the environment in which it is used.

Since our application is developed using Flutter, it is designed to run on multiple platforms, including Android, iOS, and Windows. This testing will help confirm that the app behaves as expected across different environments.

Sr. No	Test Case	Expected Result	Actual Result	Result
1	Run the mobile app on Android	App should work properly without UI or functional issues.	App tested on multiple Android devices; worked correctly.	Pass
2	Run the mobile app on iOS	App should be fully functional on iOS.	App worked as expected on multiple iOS devices.	Pass
3	Run the app on Windows	App should launch and operate normally.	App launched and functioned properly.	Pass
4	Run the app on different screen resolutions	UI should be responsive and elements undistorted.	UI adjusted correctly without layout issues.	Pass
5	Run web app in browsers (Chrome, Safari, Edge)	Layout should remain consistent across browsers.	App rendered correctly in all tested browsers.	Pass

TABLE 5.82: Compatibility Testing Table

Chapter 6

Models' Evaluation

6.1 Heart Disease Prediction

The table presents a comparative analysis of various machine learning models applied to heart disease prediction. Among the evaluated models, XGBoost Classifier achieved the highest performance with an accuracy of 74.02%, a precision of 0.747, recall of 0.722, F1-score of 0.734, and the highest ROC-AUC score of 0.81, indicating strong overall predictive capability. Other models, such as Logistic Regression and Ridge Classifier, also demonstrated competitive results with ROC-AUC scores of 0.78, but slightly lower precision and recall values. These findings suggest that XGBoost is the most effective model for this classification task.

Model	Accuracy (%)	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	ROC-AUC
Logistic Regression	73.77	0.741	0.719	0.730	0.78
Ridge Classifier	73.57	0.739	0.715	0.727	0.78
Linear SVC	73.61	0.735	0.712	0.723	0.78
ExtraTrees Classifier	73.20	0.729	0.706	0.717	0.79
XGBoost Classifier	74.02	0.747	0.722	0.734	0.81

TABLE 6.1: Model Performance Comparison

6.2 Pneumonia detection

The table summarizes the performance of various deep learning models evaluated for pneumonia detection using accuracy and recall as key metrics. The DenseNet201 model demonstrated the most balanced and effective performance, achieving an accuracy of 80.0% and a recall of 0.77, making it the final selected model. While the Fine-Tuned CNN achieved the highest accuracy of 80.76%, it had a significantly low recall of 0.32, indicating it missed many positive cases. Conversely, ResNet101 (Fine-Tuned) achieved a perfect recall of 1.00 but at the cost of extremely low accuracy (22.52%), suggesting over-sensitivity with poor specificity. Models such as EfficientNetB0 and Xception also showed promising recall scores, but DenseNet201 offered the best trade-off between accuracy and recall, making it the most reliable model for practical deployment in pneumonia detection.

Model Variant	Accuracy (%)	Recall
Basic CNN	77.5	0.71
Fine-Tuned CNN	80.76	0.32
Fine-Tuned CNN (Retry)	75.33	0.74
ResNet50 (Frozen)	77.44	0.00
ResNet101 (Frozen)	74.61	0.46
ResNet101 (Fine-Tuned)	22.52	1.00
EfficientNetB0	72.6	0.83
EfficientNetB1	77.48	0.00
Xception	78.34	0.71
DenseNet201 (Final)	80.0	0.77

TABLE 6.2: Performance Metrics of Deep Learning Models for Pneumonia Detection

Chapter 7

Conclusions and Future Direction

This study presents a comprehensive evaluation of five machine learning classifiers for the prediction of cardiovascular disease using the Sulianova dataset, a large scale, real-world clinical dataset comprising over 70,000 patient records. By systematically applying a robust preprocessing pipeline—consisting of data cleaning, outlier removal, feature engineering, and normalization—this work demonstrates that carefully prepared structured clinical data can support effective machine learning models for disease risk stratification. The performance of each classifier was evaluated using a diverse set of metrics, including accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, and area under the ROC curve, with XGBoost emerging as the top-performing model in most categories. The results confirm the established understanding that ensemble learning methods, particularly boosting-based algorithms, are capable of capturing non-linear and high order feature interactions, yielding higher predictive accuracy than classical linear models in many medical tasks. XGBoost achieved a classification accuracy of 74.02% and an ROC score of 0.81, indicating a strong ability to discriminate between individuals with and without cardiovascular disease. ExtraTrees and linear classifiers also demonstrated consistent and stable performance, highlighting the critical role of data preparation and domain-driven feature engineering. Notably, the small performance gap between linear and ensemble models emphasizes that algorithmic complexity is not always necessary to achieve clinically meaningful results. Beyond raw performance, this study underscores the importance of evaluating models from a holistic perspective. Confusion matrix analysis revealed that while XGBoost was effective overall, the number of false negatives remains clinically significant, raising concerns about missed diagnoses. In real-world healthcare settings, the consequences of failing to identify a high-risk individual can be severe, making model sensitivity a key priority. Moreover, the study also demonstrates that interpretability remains a

barrier to deploying complex models such as XGBoost in clinical environments. While feature importance rankings provide a degree of insight, the lack of case-level explainability continues to limit the trust clinicians place in algorithmic predictions. The successful application of machine learning in healthcare extends beyond statistical accuracy—it also requires attention to usability, fairness, equity, and transparency. The Sulianova dataset, while valuable for this study, is regionally and demographically specific, originating entirely from the Russian population. This raises concerns regarding the generalizability of the models to more diverse populations with different genetic, behavioral, and environmental profiles. The absence of features such as family history, lifestyle behaviors (e.g., exercise frequency, diet), medication usage, and longitudinal follow-up data also limits the scope of prediction. These factors are known to contribute meaningfully to cardiovascular outcomes and, if included, could significantly improve model performance and clinical relevance. From a systems perspective, integrating machine learning tools into clinical workflows also presents infrastructural and organizational challenges. Issues related to data availability, standardization of electronic health records, model deployment pipelines, clinician education, and real-time inference must be addressed to enable sustainable adoption. Models must also be accompanied by proper risk communication tools to ensure that outputs are presented in formats that facilitate, rather than obstruct, decision-making. Furthermore, regulatory compliance, especially around the use of black-box algorithms in medical decision-making, remains an active area of concern and policy development. Looking forward, there are several avenues for future research and expansion. First, the inclusion of multi institutional datasets representing varied ethnicities, socioeconomic backgrounds, and healthcare systems would improve model generalizability and reduce the risk of demographic bias. Second, the integration of additional feature modalities—such as clinical notes (natural language processing), ECG signals (time series), or diagnostic imaging (computer vision)—could enhance model comprehensiveness and predictive power. This would require the design of hybrid or multimodal learning architectures capable of handling both structured and unstructured data. Third, the application of deep learning models, including recurrent neural networks (RNNs) and attention-based transformers, could be explored, particularly for datasets containing temporal data such as patient monitoring or medical histories. While such models may sacrifice interpretability to some extent, the use of explainable AI (XAI) frameworks like SHAP, LIME, and counterfactual explanations could help mitigate this limitation. Research should also prioritize evaluating the trustworthiness and robustness of these models under adversarial conditions, distributional shifts, and evolving patient populations. Fourth, there

is a critical need to conduct prospective validations and pilot deployments of these models in real clinical environments. Simulation-based testing and integration with existing clinical decision support systems (CDSS) would allow researchers to monitor model behavior in situ and collect valuable feedback from medical practitioners. This step is essential for translating research grade models into actionable clinical tools and for assessing real-world impact on patient outcomes. Finally, future work should aim to incorporate fairness-aware machine learning principles to ensure equitable treatment across different patient demographics. This includes auditing models for performance disparities, applying mitigation strategies such as reweighting or adversarial debiasing, and collaborating with ethicists and social scientists to understand the broader implications of algorithmic decision-making in healthcare. In conclusion, this study affirms the potential of machine learning for cardiovascular disease prediction when grounded in rigorous preprocessing, carefully selected algorithms, and comprehensive evaluation. While ensemble models such as XGBoost show promising results, further progress depends on expanding datasets, refining interpretability, addressing deployment challenges, and embedding ethical safeguards. By pursuing these directions, the integration of machine learning into cardiology and broader clinical practice can move from experimental promise to sustainable real-world impact.

Pneumonia remains a major global health concern, with timely and accurate diagnosis being critical to effective treatment and patient recovery. The widespread use of chest X-rays in clinical diagnosis provides an opportunity for deep learning models to assist in detecting pneumonia, especially in settings where radiological expertise is limited. This study explored how various convolutional neural network (CNN) architectures could be applied to the task of pneumonia 10 detection using chest X-ray images. A comparative analysis was carried out using the RSNA Pneumonia Detection Challenge dataset, chosen for its clinical relevance and high quality radiologist-verified labels. The goal was to identify a robust model capable of not only classifying images accurately but also minimizing false negatives—a key concern in medical diagnostics. The methodology involved training a custom CNN model from scratch as a baseline, followed by a series of transfer learning experiments using six widely recognized pre-trained models: ResNet50, ResNet101, EfficientNetB0, EfficientNetB1, Xception, and DenseNet201. Each model was trained under the same preprocessing pipeline and evaluated using consistent metrics, including accuracy, recall, and AUC. These metrics were selected for their diagnostic relevance, particularly recall, which indicates a model's ability to detect actual pneumonia cases. The training was carried out using Kaggle notebooks,

where computational constraints played a role in shaping the design and feasibility of each experiment. Among the models tested, DenseNet201 emerged as the top performer, achieving the best balance across all three evaluation metrics. Its dense connectivity and effective gradient flow allowed for robust feature learning and generalization to validation data. EfficientNetB0 demonstrated high sensitivity, making it useful in high-recall clinical scenarios, but its precision and AUC fell short compared to DenseNet201. ResNet101 and EfficientNetB1, despite their depth, underperformed significantly—often showing instability or overfitting. The baseline CNN served as a useful reference but lacked the architectural capacity to compete with more advanced models. Overall, the results confirmed the value of transfer learning, especially when combined with careful fine-tuning and balanced training. In clinical applications, a model’s ability to detect true positives is more valuable than raw accuracy. DenseNet201’s strong recall and AUC scores reflect its reliability in detecting pneumonia cases without missing subtle manifestations of the disease. Its stability during training and low rate of false negatives make it a viable candidate for integration into diagnostic pipelines. The study highlights the importance of architectural choice, layer-freezing strategy, learning rate tuning, and class balancing techniques in developing effective AI tools for medical imaging. Despite the positive results, this study has several limitations that open up directions for future work. The most immediate improvement involves incorporating data augmentation techniques, such as random rotation, flipping, or contrast adjustments, which could help increase model robustness and reduce overfitting. While computational constraints on Kaggle restricted the use of ensemble models, future work could explore model fusion techniques to improve classification stability further. Similarly, explainability methods like Grad-CAM could be applied to visualize which parts of the chest X-ray contributed to a model’s prediction, enhancing transparency and clinician trust. The current study focused exclusively on classification. However, the RSNA dataset also includes bounding box annotations that can be leveraged for object detection or localization tasks. Future work could explore detection models that not only classify but also localize pneumonia-affected regions within the lungs. Additionally, segmentation models could be used to provide detailed heatmaps, offering even more insight into disease progression and severity. Such spatial understanding would be valuable in triage, treatment planning, and follow up assessments. Another critical direction involves testing the developed models on external datasets like CheXpert or real hospital data to evaluate their generalizability across different populations, equipment types, and clinical settings. Cross dataset validation would help ensure that the models are not overfitted to the RSNA dataset and are robust enough for real

world deployment. This step is essential for moving from academic research into clinical practice, where model performance must remain consistent across environments. Lastly, practical deployment pathways should be explored. This includes building lightweight inference pipelines that can be deployed on cloud servers or edge devices like hospital PACS systems or mobile diagnostic units. Collaborating with radiologists to obtain real-world feedback and performing prospective clinical trials could further validate the system's usefulness in everyday practice. With thoughtful integration and continuous improvement, deep learning systems like the ones explored in this study can serve as valuable diagnostic aids in the fight against pneumonia.

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